

PID Landscape - A Technical View

Summary	A report on work done in FAIR-IMPACT WP3 to assess the technical aspects of the PID landscape, and support the establishment of a Compliance Assessment Toolkit in FAIRCORE4EOSC, based on EOSC PID Policy as developed by the relevant task force. The results of this work is deployed operationally as the PID Knowledge Base, part of the Compliance Assessment Toolkit.
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Executive Summary

This document provides a record of the research and information gathering, analysis, and synthesis that underpins the PID Knowledge Base [197], deployed in support of the Compliance Assessment Toolkit¹ developed by the FAIRCORE4EOSC. The effort was shared between WP2 in FAIRCORE4EOSC and WP3 in FAIR-IMPACT.

The task of gathering a wide-ranging set of facts was approached from the perspective of a set of interrelated information models - summarised in a description of the **PID Landscape**², involving all stakeholders, services, and entities involved in the funding, provision, and consumption of PID services. A number of more detailed information models emerged from the analysis: the **PID Ecosystem**³, focused more narrowly on the **Actors** involved in supply and demand, an **Entity**⁴ model, describing the entities referenced by PIDs, an **Identifier**⁵ model that explains the mechanisms of identifier construction and resolution, and a comprehensive **Essential Elements**⁶ model that describes, with detailed annotations and references, the features, desirable characteristics, and attributes of PID services from the perspective of both supply and demand.

The information gathering process is supported by two emerging technologies: annotations that link individual elements in the Knowledge Base to sources with fine granularity⁷, and validated generative AI sources that are described in detail and also included at record-level granularity into the Knowledge Base. DANS is working towards a policy and protocols for the responsible and transparent application of AI⁸ in automated curation, and this effort assisted with development of good practices and its implementation.

The main objective of the work done in support of the Compliance Assessment Toolkit is **improvement in quality assurance in the PID Ecosystem**. The work assisted not only with gathering a substantial body of information about best practices and guidance in this respect⁹, but also to identify gaps in a variety of aspects that serve as the main set of informal recommendations from this report (Conclusions and Recommendations, and Annexure F). In broad terms, these deal with governance, policy, harmonisation of features of PID services, identification of poor practices, capacity building, and **improvements in monitoring of persistence and resolvability**: these are, after all, the main implicit value of PIDs.

¹ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/compliance-assessment-toolkit-cat>

² [Annexure A.1](#)

³ [Annexure A.3](#)

⁴ [Annexure A.2](#)

⁵ [Annexure B.1.4](#)

⁶ 'Consolidation of Evidence'

⁷ Using e.g. hypothes.is. There are 175 annotations to date: <https://hypothes.is/users/WHPrivate?q=PID>

⁸ Contact the author for more information

⁹ Included in the Knowledge Base, but also published in part by FAIR-IMPACT [189].

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Glossary

A comprehensive glossary has been developed as part of the PID Knowledge Base, and this can be accessed [here](#). The terms below are used with specific meaning in the document, and are highlighted for convenience:

Actors	The EOSC PID Policy defines a number of actors (Roles) that in combination offer a PID service. Typically, an Authority provides the namespace management mechanisms to ensure uniqueness of identifiers, and mostly, but not always, the identifier syntax is based on a Scheme that may be formalised as a Standard maintained by a Standards Body . The Authority can provide a central registry of all identifiers in a scheme, or make use of decentralised or federated registries. Typically, a service is offered by a Provider based on the infrastructure and standards derived from the Authority and the Scheme. Managers of PID Services usually rely on the Provider to create and maintain a kernel metadata schema, and assists the Owners of referenced entities to provide the requisite metadata and to maintain Resolution: the link between the identifier and the content that it identifies ¹⁰ .	
PID Stack	A specific set of services and actors (Authorities, Schemes, Providers, and Multi-Provider Agencies), supported by standardisation, resolution mechanisms, and namespace management that results in a branded or unique PID service to PID Managers. Stacks can reuse services provided by Actors - for example the same Scheme can be used by many Stacks.	[0]
PID Landscape	The PID Landscape refers to a loosely coupled collection of services, end users, and governance mechanisms that impact either users, services, or both - in essence, the supply of and demand for PID services and the rules that govern the exchange.	[0]
PID Ecosystem	The PID Ecosystem refers more specifically to the collection of standards, services, actors, and roles that enable PID Stacks to provide their services, together with the specific end users of PID Stacks.	[0]

A comprehensive set of vocabularies are published and maintained by FAIRCORE4EOSC to support the Compliance Assessment Toolkit, and this report makes use of these definitions and lists whenever it is useful. A summary of the main vocabularies in use is presented below.

- [Criteria Imperatives](#)¹¹: A local implementation of the contents of [RFC 2119](#)¹².
- [EOSC PID Policy Roles](#)¹³: A list of Actors and Stakeholders identified for the EOSC PID Policy, and participating in the PID ecosystem.
- [General Glossary of PID Terms](#)¹⁴.

¹⁰ See detail in Section

¹¹ <https://mscr-vocabularies-test.2.rahtiapp.fi/terminology/438b7eb5-83c5-4ccc-8f85-0f583d148519>

¹² <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc2119>

¹³ <https://mscr-vocabularies-test.2.rahtiapp.fi/terminology/9c735525-960e-4f13-a74d-4eb23ea9c308>

¹⁴ <https://mscr-vocabularies-test.2.rahtiapp.fi/terminology/3af07c11-11a7-42ed-b0e4-d22cbeb367fb>

- [Glossary for Compliance Assessment](#)¹⁵: The terminology in this glossary is based on a conceptual model for compliance assessment, developed for and maintained by the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.
- [Metric and Benchmark Types](#)¹⁶: These types provide common combinations of metrics and benchmarks.
- [Motivation Typology](#)¹⁷: The reason for or origin of a set of principles, rules, a policy, or objectives.
- [Predictability](#)¹⁸: Indication of the extent to which independent assessors will reach similar results given the same input.
- [Test Result Typology](#)¹⁹: The typical types returned by a test.
- [Test Typology](#)²⁰: A formalisation of the test types used by CAT.

¹⁵ <https://mscr-vocabularies-test.2.rahtiapp.fi/terminology/2a062144-1766-40e7-b8da-6a4b1d5f9f00>

¹⁶ <https://mscr-vocabularies-test.2.rahtiapp.fi/terminology/e30f5d62-9b60-49c0-bf4f-d5e58eb2b1e1>

¹⁷ <https://mscr-vocabularies-test.2.rahtiapp.fi/terminology/a9ceb5a3-15ca-4e95-908f-36cab72014a2>

¹⁸ <https://mscr-vocabularies-test.2.rahtiapp.fi/terminology/c7dde918-9433-4d22-8e5f-346d808a6d52>

¹⁹ <https://mscr-vocabularies-test.2.rahtiapp.fi/terminology/3c897302-bb60-49f5-ab1c-23b08867cd68>

²⁰ <https://mscr-vocabularies-test.2.rahtiapp.fi/terminology/525d5237-5053-4c61-8724-1fee00fa2a>

Context

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) have been specified as “an abstraction layer that arbitrates between the reference of a digital object and its location” [91]. This rather conceptual definition can be contrasted with one from [ISO 5127:2017](#) (Information and documentation - Foundation and vocabulary): “unique identifier that ensures permanent access for a digital object by providing access to it independently of its physical location or current ownership”. One might argue that this definition is too onerous for a large number of PID services to satisfy, and we discuss the [nature and expectations of persistence](#) in detail in the Annexures.

In this document, we present an analysis of the technical aspects of the **PID Ecosystem**: the inventories of and relationships between major actors and services in the landscape, the standards and standards bodies that maintain and manage the basis of PID schemes, and the entities that are represented by these PIDs. An analysis of the scope of functionality offered by PID systems, and the features desired by the end user community is also done - a broader **PID Landscape**. The use cases and workflows in which the end user community applies PIDs is analysed, structured, and classified in the process. See [‘Methodology’](#) for more information.

The **objectives** we hope to achieve or support with this work are as follows:

1. Creation of a **knowledge base** that describes the PID Ecosystem, and is available as an extension of the EOSC PID Policy Compliance work being done in the [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#) project ([Compliance Assessment Toolkit - CAT](#)). In this role, it serves as additional input in respect of commonly adopted PIDs for specific use cases that link to the guidance offered to end users of the CAT.
2. Serving as a basis for **systematic recording and contextualisation of best practices** in respect of the policies applicable to PID use in the community, and the application of PIDs. This work is being done in the [FAIR-IMPACT](#) project, Work Package 3, and by linking these outputs to the knowledge base, it is possible to present and apply it in the CAT as guidance.
3. Defining the scope of PID applications, its benefits and limitations (and how each PID maps to a set of structured features and characteristics expected of PIDs) will assist the end user community with **selection of appropriate PIDs** (significantly extending tools that exist for this purpose). It may be possible to extend the CAT to offer such guidance, and the FAIR-IMPACT project will be able to use this information and supporting software to engage the community - supporting their goal of **improving the use of PIDs in the community** and to align it with best practices.
4. Supporting several exchanges of information and engagements with the [EOSC PID Policy Task Force](#) prior to the end of its mandate (early 2024):
 - a. Ensuring that the best practices documented here are incorporated into the PID Policy as applicable;

- b. Verifying that the scope of PID use, as confirmed through desktop research and FAIR-IMPACT engagement with the community is reflected in the policy and that the policy does not exclude widely adopted practices or services through omission.
5. There is a steady growth in the number of PID services, and these ‘emerging PID Stacks’ are often technically mature but lack soft infrastructure²¹ expected by the community. It is an express intent of the work presented in this report, supplemented by the accompanying Knowledge Base, to **assist emerging services** with understanding and establishing the soft infrastructure requirements.

Methodology

The following approach is used in this report:

1. A landscape assessment and analysis of the PID ecosystem, largely based on a [comprehensive review of literature](#) and web-based resources, is used to determine the **characteristics of supply and demand** of persistent identifiers.
 - a. From this, we are able to derive a set of Information Models: defining the language by which we describe the landscape ([Annexure A](#)).
 - b. **Supply is characterised by service offerings** that (in most cases) require a number of actors and components to be present and functioning properly, and that are distinguished from one another by the **features and attributes** that they offer within **elements of service**. These elements cover topics such as functions, performance, cost, governance, and integrity, amongst others. We review a sizable number of publications and web resources with an objective to **describe, understand and structure** information about the supply of persistent identifiers ([Annexure B](#)).
 - c. **Demand is characterised by use cases**, and these cases often also require more than one actor to make a contribution at a **minimum level of performance**. The actors are not likely to be exactly the same as those involved in supply, but there is an overlap. **Not all use cases require the same type of service offering**, and we will attempt to describe this diversity in a structured way ([Annexure C](#)).
2. Based on a review of typical use cases, we will attempt to characterise them using the same set of elements, features, and attributes that describe supply offerings. This allows us to **develop a conceptual model** that can describe and characterise both supply and demand, and supports the **matching of supply and demand based on shared characteristics** ([Annexure D](#)).
3. This input is used to structure surveys of PID Authorities, Providers, Managers and Owners, which confirm, refine, and extend the contents of the knowledge base.

²¹

4. The persistent identifier ecosystem is complex, with a requirement that several actors and components perform at a minimum level of competence for a successful outcome. **To ensure this minimum level of competence one needs a variety of instruments to be available.** These instruments have different focus areas, ranging from governance-related ones such as policies, through technical aspects (such as standards, benchmarks and best practices) to capacity concerns (guidance, training, and so on). We make an **initial survey of the scope of these instruments** and the contribution they make in the ecosystem ([Annexure E](#)). Based on this, we develop an **inventory of best practices**.
5. It may be possible to **identify gaps in the ecosystem**: use cases for which services are poorly matched or do not exist, and services for which few or no use cases are evident ([Annexure F](#)).

The information models, together with structured data and information based on them and derived from the comprehensive literature review and workshop results, are combined into a Knowledge Base on PIDs that can be used for future community benefit ([Annexure G](#)).

Annotations

In this document and its supplementary materials, substantial use is made of annotated references. References are annotated with an additional set of tags, in part from a glossary, and this allows others to navigate to specific locations in web resources where evidence, assertions, or information in support of the work can be found.

An example of such an annotation is provided here:

[61] “... Ultimately the knowledge graph will permit a much clearer understanding of global research networks, research impact, and the ways in which knowledge is created in a highly interconnected world.”

<https://hyp.is/kAuFzl4XEe6rLLfP9TEvKg/popjournal.ca/issue03/goddard>²²

This link will take the reader directly to the location in the web resource where the text can be found, and is annotated with one or more glossary terms so that these items can easily be found again and can be filtered for specific tags. In a simple way, this creates a knowledge graph of web resources used in the document, and if the tags are Linked Open Data URIs, it links the text snippets (assertions) into a wider knowledge graph.

An example of the value of such annotation can be found by searching the [hypothes.is](#) site for one the tags we use: “[PID Use Cases](#)”. We can also retrieve these annotations through the API, as in this example for [all annotations related to the FAIR-IMPACT WP3 work](#).

Use of Generative AI Services

Artificial Intelligence, and specifically generative AI based on LLMs, e.g. [Perplexity](#) and [OpenAI](#), is directly suited to the sourcing and validation of information about the ecosystem and the landscape. We use Artificial Intelligence in two distinct ways in this work:

²² To test this, download and install the [hypothes.is](#) plug-in for your browser.

1. **Validation of scope:** in this case, AI is used to confirm the scope of landscape assessment results. For example, if literature review and survey of actors determines that there are a specific number of business models in use by Providers, AI can be used to confirm this conclusion. In these cases, human effort is ‘reviewed’ by AI.
2. **Sourcing of details:** it is extremely time-consuming to source detailed characteristics from desk research. For example, determining the date of first use of a PID service requires extensive web search and careful reading of results by humans, whereas AI services can answer such a query in near real time. For such cases, AI effort is reviewed and validated by humans, and some AI services now provide verifiable references for their results.

In both these application examples, we follow the emergent DANS AI Policy to ensure maximum transparency. This entails recording the context of each use of AI, including model versions, dates, prompts, and responses, and annotating such instances of AI use with an identifier that is stored at fine granularity in the resulting knowledge base data. See the example of such a reference in Table 1.

Table 1: Referencing the Use of Generative AI

Identifier	Model	Date of Use	Prompt	Response
Pid_graph: 7D9662D5AP	ChatGPT 4o mini	19-11-2024	Can you determine when the IGSN ID was first used, and how many have been issued ?	The International Generic Sample Number (IGSN) system was first launched in 2011. It provides globally unique and persistent identifiers for physical samples, initially targeting geosciences but now used across various disciplines to facilitate sample identification, citation, and metadata integration. Since its inception, over 10 million IGSN IDs have been registered. In 2022, IGSN partnered with DataCite to integrate its identifiers into the DataCite DOI system, broadening its reach and standardizing its use across disciplines

Future Updates and Process Automation

The first release of the PID Knowledge Base, as described in this document, was by necessity time-consuming and required significant human input. Our intention is to continue to automate and refine the processes whereby the knowledge base is maintained, and to open up its curation to qualified individuals and organisations. The table below defines the future perspective on automation and updating.

Table 2: State of Information Completeness and Future Plans

Aspect	Current status	Future aims
Information Models	Manually created by way of literature and landscape review, community input	This will not change, a sensible review cycle needs to be determined - say every 2 years. Future governance should include formation of a working group to manage the vocabularies, information models, and desirable characteristics.
Vocabulary	Manually identified, extended, or created depending on the situation.	
Desirable Characteristics	Manual synthesis from landscape review, supplemented by AI scope validations.	
Use Cases	Manual synthesis from landscape review, supplemented by AI scope validations.	Automated maintenance using refined (RAG) AI models, reviewed by humans in two ways: surveys to confirm data, and curator review.
Service and Ecosystem Characteristics	AI use to determine data values, reviewed by humans, and confirmed via surveys	
Policy Compliance	Already automated, contains external tests for aspects such as availability, resolvability, and persistence.	Continue using automated updates, and extend external tests to include AI-supplemented information gathering - for example existence of relevant evidence, and additional AI-supported tests, such as estimates of content drift over time.

The Landscape

The landscape for persistent identifiers refers to a loosely coupled collection of services, end users, and governance mechanisms that impact either users, services, or both - in essence, the supply of and demand for PID services and the rules that govern the exchange. There are many stakeholders in the landscape that are not directly involved in the provision of services, but are nevertheless dependent on its quality, success, or breadth of adoption, are involved in funding elements of the landscape, or stand to either benefit from implementation or be disadvantaged by challenges.

In [Annexure A.1](#), we present a detailed information model for the PID landscape, defining the roles of and relations between major elements. These include, *inter alia*

- Service Providers - bringing PID services to the users of such services and supporting the main workflows and use cases they want to implement.
- Intermediaries - infrastructure and organisations that assist users with service uptake or to gain access to services, and often play an important role in maintaining the relationship between identifiers and the concepts or things they reference.
- End Users - the stakeholders that benefit directly from the use of persistent identifiers.
- Dependencies - many of the role-players are dependent on the performance, sustainability, and service levels of other elements in the landscape. We define this ecosystem in more detail in the following section.
- Stakeholders: there are stakeholders that benefit indirectly from the successful implementation of PID services - for example, funders and national drivers for adoption and implementation of Open Science.

Entities

The entities referenced by PIDs require some consideration. There are a number of classification schemes that are of relevance, for example those for bibliographic materials (FABIO, [175]), Schema.org [188], the US Library of Congress (LoC) [189], and a classification of resource outputs by COAR [185]. While these classifications have some benefits, such as being well-established and having stable URIs, they do not cover the full spectrum of entities that can be referenced by PIDs. Other classifications are also in widespread use, for example the entity types defined by DataCite and Zenodo for their metadata schema [186], and by [CERIF](#)²³.

[Annexure A.2](#) elaborates the registry developed for referencing Entities as concepts, which follows the approach of developing a broad scope and hierarchy based on observed Entities in our literature review, and then extending this with the terms and stable URIs found in the FABIO, COAR, LoC, Schema.org, and DataCite vocabularies. Wherever possible, we use a URI from schema.org and/ or WikiData to serve as a common (canonical) reference in cases where multiple URIs are available for the same concept.

Stakeholders

The stakeholder community involved in the use of PIDs, and in its direct and indirect benefits is equivalent to the academic or public research enterprise and its stakeholders [47], [61]. A registry of Stakeholder Types has been developed based on occurrences and references in use cases, and this serves as a starting point for annotating the Knowledge Base with use cases and expected benefits of applying PIDs.

We distinguish two superclasses of Stakeholder Types: *Organisations or Institutions* (e.g. Libraries or Funders), and *Groups of Individuals* with the same interests or requirements (e.g. Researchers or Data Stewards). See [Annexure C.2](#).

Actors in the Landscape

The EOSC PID Policy [35] provides a starting point for the characterisation of the actors and roles involved in the PID ecosystem - the governance, services, standards, and management required to ensure that persistent identifiers are unique and remain resolvable over time, as well as a characterisation of the end user community. The actors defined in the policy have been extended to include roles observed in the literature. [Annexure A.3](#) describes the actors and roles in detail, and a formal vocabulary for Actors and Roles has been published.

Supply of Persistent Identifiers

There is a large number of persistent identifiers available to end users, but the exact scope depends on how narrowly the term is defined. The term is generally associated with a small number of

²³ <https://cerif.eurocris.org/vocab/xml/OutputTypes.xml>

mainstream services (ARK, ORCID, DOIs, Handle, and so on), but in reality, there are many more that are widely in use, and while many are not seen as PIDs²⁴, the expectation that these identifiers will be stable, well-managed, and persistent is implicit. ***Inclusion of these identifiers into linked open data relations and using them to make data or metadata semantically interoperable assumes long-term availability.***

In defining the scope of identifiers of interest, one should also take note of those that are explicitly non-academic in its application or origin- for example car registration numbers, VAT numbers, or personal identity numbers. These identifiers are not commonly used in research and development contexts, but ***should be used by preference when these entities are the subjects of research.***

[Annexure A.4](#) provides an overview of the supply of persistent identifiers, together with a review of some mainstream services.

The Concept of a Service Offering or ‘PID Stack’

PID Stacks are based on interdependent actors (components and roles) that collectively provide the means to serve the end user community and offer them a PID Service. Several actors and roles in the ecosystem contribute to more than one PID Stack²⁵. Some PID stacks are complex (for example CrossRef or DataCite DOIs, with many institutions and services contributing to the stack), whereas some are very simple (e.g. ORCID and SWHID, where almost all roles are performed by a single institution).

The use of some services across multiple stacks raises interesting considerations: on the one hand, economy of scale, quality, and efficiency are improved through shared infrastructure, but it also creates single points of failure for more than one stack or service.

The Knowledge Base being developed as a companion to this report identifies approximately 130 PID Stacks²⁶ that are in scope at the time of writing, and that will grow over time as new services emerge or are identified. [Annexure A.4](#) provides a definition of PID Stacks as well as several examples.

Emerging PID Stacks

There is a steady growth in the number of PID services, driven by either demand for such services or by a need identified by the service community from a process perspective. These ‘emerging PID Stacks’ are often technically mature lacking in soft infrastructure²⁷ expected by the community. It is an express intent of the work presented in this report, supplemented by the accompanying Knowledge Base, to assist emerging services with understanding and establishing the soft infrastructure requirements.

²⁴ For example vocabulary concepts and terms used in a linked open data context

²⁵ For example: many PID Stacks are based on the Handle System.

²⁶ This includes identifiers for concepts, and for digital and physical objects.

²⁷ For example guidance, value added services, continuity planning and sustainability. See [B.4](#) for a review.

Evidence for Desirable Characteristics

It is clear from review of literature that there are a wide-ranging number of features, attributes, and properties (collectively: characteristics) that the community expects from PID services [2], [5], [6], [11], [28]. In addition, PID services, authorities, and schemes often advertise or emphasise their benefits and distinguishing features [2]. A synthesis of these characteristics - with a resulting assessment of gaps in expectation fulfilment - is an important aspect of the work reported in this document. It serves as a basis for selection of an appropriate persistent identifier service or stack for a specific application, and by mapping the sets of characteristics to quality assurance mechanisms (such as the EOSC PID Policy or the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI)), there is also a mechanism available to determine whether these mechanisms adequately address the scope of desirable characteristics.

The review of these characteristics also lead to a concrete set of outputs that can be used by the community and is included into CAT: a set of guidelines and best practices, applicable to each of the main actors in the ecosystem. A formal deliverable produced by FAIR-IMPACT [189] focuses on the guidelines for PID Managers, but guidelines for the other actors form part of the Knowledge Base and will be available via the CAT.

Characterisation of Service Offerings

The characteristics of PID services were inventoried and then categorised based on a comprehensive review of web resources describing these services (see references). The categorisation was developed in this report, and broadly describes the following groups of characteristics:

- **Functionality:** in addition to the obvious aspects such as uniqueness, resolution, and persistence, also aspects of how content variability is managed, whether there are standard kernel metadata schema, how scalable the service is, and whether the PID is technology-independent.
- **Performance:** aspects of governance, sustainability (technical and financial), value addition, and service levels.
- **Service Topology:** centralisation, decentralisation, federation, hierarchical, peer to peer, ...
- **Cost:** Mechanisms for cost recovery and explicit vs. invisible costs
- **Mitigation:** Mechanisms (non-technical and technical) to mitigate against common issues with PIDs, e.g. content drift and link rot.
- **Definition:** Attributes that further define the PID service but do not directly affect its performance or functionality, such as the organisations involved in the Stack, number of PIDs registered to date, and similar properties.

Expectations in terms of functionality, cost and performance are sometimes formalised by way of e.g.

the EOSC PID Policy [35], national strategies [43] or institutional policies [103], and community consensus such as Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI) [27]. These expectations and best practices were collated with characteristics offered by PID services to provide a comprehensive inventory.

[Annexure B](#) provides a detailed review of the characteristics of PID services and stacks, collated with community expectations.

Mapping PID Stacks to Desirable Characteristics

It is obvious that not all PID services and stacks will satisfy all desirable characteristics, and this is not always necessary, since the ***use case determines the required characteristics***. For this reason, it is important that best practices, guidelines, and criteria or provisions included into policies and similar quality assurance mechanisms distinguish broadly defined generic use cases.

It has proven difficult to research the degree to which PID services cover the desired characteristics, and to ensure that the Knowledge Base contains the most comprehensive detail possible, a survey of PID Managers, Providers and Authorities has been developed in collaboration between FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT. An engagement programme to execute the survey has been developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC, and once this has been completed by a reasonable number of respondents, the Knowledge Base will be updated.

Requirement Levels: Mandatory and Optional Characteristics

In addition to the nuances introduced by use cases, not all characteristics are strong recommendations for implementation by all actors. It is therefore important to use consistent language to define whether offering such characteristics, or following a guideline or recommendation is considered mandatory or optional. Standard definitions of keywords to indicate requirement levels have been used in this report and in the Knowledge Base [190].

Consolidation of Evidence

Figure 1: Scope and classification of desirable characteristics

Figure 1 shows the high-level scope and classification of desirable characteristics of PID services and stacks, which in turn serves as the basis of organisation of the Knowledge Base. For each characteristic, the following information is linked where available:

1. Evidence by way of references and annotations for the practices and guidelines associated with the characteristic;
2. A mapping to the actor(s) expected to align with or implement the best practice, together with the level required (mandatory or optional);

3. A mapping to the entities for which such a characteristic is required;
4. An indication of the use cases that require the characteristic; and
5. A mapping to the PID services and stacks that implement or provide the characteristic, if applicable.

The Knowledge Base is implemented as a relational database at present, but deployment as a Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG) is planned. To support this, each relevant node is represented by a URI, and the relations between nodes are predefined. Figure 2 depicts the scope of the Knowledge Base.

Figure 2: Knowledge Base - Information Model for the PID Landscape²⁸

Some of the nodes in the information model (for example the ‘PID Stack’ node, the ‘Actors and Roles’ node, or the ‘desirable Characteristics’ node) lead to a more detailed information model. Refer to Annexure A for descriptions of the information model and its detailed components.

The Knowledge Base structure and deployment is described in detail in a separate document [197].

Analysis and Characterisation of Use Cases

Understanding the motivation for implementing and using PIDs starts with use cases. It is self-evident that not all use cases will need all of the desirable characteristics of PID stacks and services to be

²⁸ The model will change as new information is obtained that may not fit the model. The authoritative version can be found [here](#) (may require a [browser plug-in](#) to work).

available, and it's also clear that most high level policies (for example the EOSC PID Policy) do not make allowance for situations where the level (or absence) of implementation is aligned with a specific use case.

Use Cases

We inventoried a number of use cases from literature surveys²⁹, and developed a first draft of generalisation of these use cases ([Annexure C](#)).

- **Categorisation of Use Cases:** each use case was categorised into a higher-level class reflecting the intent of the use case.
- **Expected Benefits:** For each use case, the benefit expected from PID use by the implementor or end user was recorded, and these benefits were standardised and categorised as well.
- **Use Case Elements:** Use cases were assessed for the common, granular elements that they share, and an inventory of use case elements was developed iteratively from this process.
- **Actor-Specific Use Cases:** Not all use cases or use case elements involve all actors, and those in scope are linked to the use case.
- **Persistent Identifier Selection:** The use case elements are sometimes linked to specific PID services or stacks - both by definition of the entities involved, and the PID stacks or services identified for use³⁰.

Workflows

Workflows are defined as multi-step processes that are repeatable with reasonable predictability, and are documented or encoded to accomplish this³¹. In the report, a generic classification of workflows was developed.

Figure 2 defines the relationship between use cases and its elements, and workflows. These relationships, and the inventories of use case elements and workflows identified thus far are discussed in detail in [Annexure C.3](#).

The Knowledge Base defines the characteristics and context for use cases and workflows, based on the approach described in Table 3.

²⁹ 28 use cases at the time of writing, supplemented by AI-based information retrieval.

³⁰ Detailed information on this is not easily available. Our surveys will extend the available information.

³¹ “defined sequence of activities of an organisational entity, enabled by the systematic organisation of resources into processes that transform materials, provide services, or process information” - Wikidata - <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q627335>

Table 3: Characterisation of Workflows and Use Cases

Stakeholder(s)	Identify the stakeholder(s) from the appropriate inventory <i>Examples: Researcher, Funder</i>
Workflow	Identify the workflow from the appropriate inventory <i>Example: Grant Application Process</i>
Use Case	Description of the use case <i>Example: User describes prior research in scope for an open call response</i>
Use Case Elements	Identify granular elements of the use case from inventory of elements <i>Examples: Unambiguous identification of applicant and research outputs</i>
PID Services/ Stacks	The PID Services or stacks to be used, selected from the registry <i>Examples: ORCID, DOI</i>
Benefits	The benefits expected, selected from an inventory <i>Examples: Efficiency, Precision, Aggregation</i>
Actors Involved	Identify actors involved in the use case <i>Examples: Authority/ Provider, Owner</i>

Implementation

Implementation of PID services span a wide variety of use cases and workflows, as indicated in the previous section. For all of these, a minimum level of performance and quality of service is required. These considerations are not yet directly addressed in the knowledge base. It was, however, possible to inventorise the scope of performance levels and quality of service, based on material reviewed in the landscape analysis. This is discussed in more detail in [Annexure E](#).

Ensuring Quality of Service

We propose a set of considerations aimed at improvement of quality of service, broadly focused on four categories:

1. **Governance-focused:** measures that can be taken at the level of governance, for example by developing policies and ensuring that they are implemented

2. **Technology-focused:** these include development and promotion of standards and specifications, creation and maintenance of common vocabularies and registries, and supporting infrastructure such as the Compliance Assessment Toolkit and the Knowledge Base.
3. **Performance-focused:** ensuring that the community expectations and benchmarks in respect of minimum performance is developed and adopted by the ecosystem
4. **Capacity-focused:** developing and disseminating best practices in respect of implementation.

Matching Use Cases with Services

By developing the Knowledge base and presenting it in such a way that individual PID services and stacks can be discovered on the basis of a number of user-focused facets, selection of appropriate PIDs for a specific use case becomes possible. ***An additional future consideration would be to collect annotation information from end users, extending and refining the use cases linked to specific PID services and the entities that are being referenced in the use cases.***

Implementation Gaps

The following implementation gaps are evident from our literature survey, knowledge base construction, and public engagements³²:

1. **Governance and Policy:**
 - a. **Scope:** Existing policies, for example the EOSC PID Policy, do not fully cover characteristics and features expected by the end user community, and may require extension as a result.
 - b. **Mandate:** Moreover, such policies lack mandates and assessment or verification authorities at the present time.
 - c. **Effective Engagement:** the work done by FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT to date contains numerous aspects of improvement and harmonisation applicable to the Provider/ Authority community, but there is no formal mechanism for engagement.
2. **Features:** Not all PID services exhibit a common, interoperable set of features that will be required to assess the quality of service from an end user perspective (***‘Harmonisation’***). This aspect links to some extent to the performance gaps discussed below, since some commonly implemented features are required to properly assess performance. Multiple approaches are available to achieve improvement, including FDO [193], and Signposting [105].
3. **Performance Gaps:** There are numerous performance gaps that were identified, but perhaps the most important of these involve the two critical characteristics of PIDs: persistence and

³² EOSC Winter Schools 2024, 2025, and the FAIR Impact Support Action for PID Managers.

resolvability. For neither of these, consistent and verified public evidence is available across the PID services

4. **Information Gaps:** There are several topics for which significant information gaps exist,, or for which information structuring and presentation can be improved.
 - a. **Policy Implementation:**
 - b. **PID Strategy and Policy:** Future national, network, or institutional PID strategies and policies can benefit from structured reporting of benefits, use cases, and workflows, and the information created in the Knowledge Base, and from the recommendations made by FAIRCORE4EOSC in respect of policy structure and components [101].

Annexure F provides a synopsis of the issues and gaps identified during the course of our work.

Conclusions and Recommendations

1. *Gaps and Issues*

- a. **Governance-related:** In a separate process, FAIRCORE4EOSC, with assistance from FAIR-IMPACT, have initiated a conversation in the EOSC Federation stakeholder community via EOSC [Opportunity Area 1](#)³³ to improve governance and mandate-related aspects. This report serves as additional details for that discussion.
- b. **Community Governance and Ownership:** The information models, knowledge base, vocabularies, and registries created by FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT require significant community input in respect of maintenance and extension, and it is not clear how and where such involvement should be managed. A start could be made within the EOSC Opportunity Area 1 activities, but a more formal affiliation, either within future EOSC Federation structures or the RDA are better alternatives.
- c. **Meaningful, Effective Engagement:** a properly mandated or endorsed structure is required to engage in well-governed discussion with the supply side (Providers, Authorities) on behalf of the demand side (Managers, Owners) in the EOSC community. This may have to extend to be a global forum.
- d. **Best Practices and Guidance:** It was possible to develop a ‘starter kit’ of guidance and best practices - covering specifically the completion of PID Policy-related tests, and implementation guidance for Managers. This leaves obvious gaps in respect of other Actors and guidance on metrics, benchmarks, criteria and principles.
- e. **AI-Ready Strategies and Policies:** structuring the content of PID policies and strategies using the vocabularies developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT, and by following the structuring guidance proposed by FAIRCORE4EOSC, granular

³³ <https://eosc.eu/oa1-pids-persistent-identifiers/>

annotation and inclusion of these resources into Knowledge Graphs will be simplified significantly.

- f. **Harmonisation:** there are at least two approaches to the improvement of machine actionability and readability of the metadata associated with a PID - centralisation (as exemplified by FDO) and distributed decentralisation (as in Signposting) [144]. Work is ongoing in FAIR-IMPACT WP3, with inputs from FAIRCORE4EOSC WP2 to develop reasoned advice and best practices.
- g. **Completeness:** the resources available in the FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects are, of course, finite, and several areas for improvement of the coverage and granularity of the Knowledge Base will remain at project completion in May 2025. These will be documented for future reference.

2. *Future Perspectives*

- a. **AI-Generated Content:** It is relatively simple and efficient to source a wide variety of Knowledge Base content using AI-supported methods. For the initial release, these inputs were manually verified and moderated, but protocols are needed to improve efficiency (e.g. eliminate unnecessary human moderation where possible) and to improve accuracy³⁴.
- b. **Community Curation:** this approach is used (with unknown success rate) by FAIRSharing to curate content that was originally gathered by the FAIRSharing service. Implementing such a feature may not be particularly difficult, and can also serve as a verification step for AI-generated content in the Knowledge Base.
- c. **Use Cases and Workflows:** One of the major gaps that we have identified is comprehensive, fine-grained information about the use cases, benefits, and workflows where end users require the use of PID services in one way or another. Such information can be collected via annotation from end users, extending and refining the use cases linked to specific PID services and the entities that are being referenced in the use cases.
- d. **Benchmarks:** Assessment is fundamentally based on comparison of a measured value (obtained via a standardised test) with a **benchmark** to provide a metric (such as 'pass' or 'fail'). The benchmarks included in the Compliance Assessment Toolkit have been proposed by the FAIRCORE4EOSC development team, but requires a process of community discussion and validation to make them realistic and aligned with both the capabilities of the supply-side and the expectations of the demand-side.

³⁴ Recent developments that utilise Knowledge Graphs to serve as a basis for request formulation and response moderation for generative AI models holds promise [203]

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There are a large number of additional references that are not explicitly included in the document, but are used to substantiate data elements in the Knowledge Base itself. These are supplemented by recorded and referenced instances of AI application to retrieve data values on specific topics or properties from language models through generative AI. These reference lists will be published as supplementary materials with this document.

Annexure A: Characterising the Landscape

We use two terms with regularity: The PID Landscape and the PID Ecosystem. The **PID Landscape** refers to a loosely coupled collection of services, end users, and governance mechanisms that impact either users, services, or both - in essence, the supply of and demand for PID services and the rules that govern the exchange. It also includes a variety of stakeholders that rely on these services. The **PID Ecosystem** refers more specifically to the collection of standards, services, actors, and roles that enable a specific **PID Stack** to provide a service, together with the specific end users of the PID Stack. There can potentially be other ecosystems in the landscape, but these are not covered in the report.

A.1 Information Model - Stakeholders and Relationships

The model is derived iteratively by gathering information about the landscape, and noting the main nodes, and the relations between them, with amendments and refinements added as required.

Figure A.1.1 Information Model for the PID Landscape³⁵ [0]

Model elements are discussed below.

- **Stakeholders:** Stakeholders are the beneficial users of **PID Stacks**, and can be classified into **Groups** (mostly roles filled by individuals) and **Institutions** [47], [61] (See Annexure C.2 for details).

³⁵ The model will change as new information is obtained that may not fit the model. The authoritative version can be found [here](#) (requires a [browser plug-in](#) to work).

- The Stakeholders benefit from implementation of a number of **Use Cases**, but these use cases are generally not well structured or standardised, and are described arbitrarily in terms of scope and granularity. It is possible to extract common **Use Case Elements**, and these can be included into more structured and well-defined (possibly machine-actionable) **Workflows** (as, for example, [53]).
- Stakeholders then execute one or more Workflows in practice to obtain the **Benefits** of PID Stacks. This is possible because the PID Stacks provide (offer) Benefits via their [Desirable Characteristics](#), and use cases are satisfied in part or completely by these characteristics.
- The PID Stacks are overwhelmingly used to *persistently and unambiguously identify and resolve* [Entities](#) - which can be **Concepts** or **Things** (there are many additional child entities - see sections below). Moreover, there is a large collection of **Entities**, and we have developed a separate detailed classification of these for use in characterisation of the PID Stacks used to identify them (See Appendix C.4).
- Some PID Stacks may offer additional **Content Negotiation** [154] or Inflection [99] that provides more **Benefits** beyond persistent identification and resolution, and these include exposure of PID kernel metadata³⁶, linking to additional information, version histories, and distinguishing links to the object, its context [105], and its authoritative metadata.
- The Workflows are ideally based on **Best Practices**, and such Best Practices are in turn defined and refined by a review of the most commonly adopted workflows, use case elements, and PID Stacks in the community.
- The Best Practices also ensure that Desirable Characteristics of PID Stacks are fully utilised.
- PID Stacks are implemented (operationalised) by a combination of [Actors](#) in the ecosystem, and in some cases, elements of the PID ecosystem are common to multiple stacks.
- The **Policy** developed for EOSC should ensure that the most important Desirable Characteristics of PID Stacks (potentially for Different Use cases or Workflows) are guaranteed to the Stakeholders by assigning compliance criteria to Actors. This aspect links to the Conceptual (Information) Model developed for FAIRCORE4EOSC, and which will underpin the [Compliance Assessment Toolkit](#) for EOSC PID Policy [66].

A.2 Classification of Entities Described by PIDs

The entities referenced by PIDs require some consideration. There are a number of classification schemes that are of relevance, for example those for bibliographic materials (FABIO, [175]), Schema.org [188], the US Library of Congress (LoC) [189], and a classification of resource outputs by COAR [185]. While these classifications have some benefits, for example being well-established and having stable URIs, they do not cover the full spectrum of entities that can be referenced by PIDs.

³⁶ For a more detailed discussion, see [B.1.6: 'Metadata'](#). There are multiple ways to extend the benefits of PIDs in machine actionable ways, and FAIR Data Objects (FDO), and Signposting are two examples.

Other classifications are also in widespread use, for example the entity types defined by DataCite and Zenodo for their metadata schema [186], and by [CERIF](#)³⁷

The entities referenced by persistent identifiers can be classified in terms of whether they are objects or are an abstract concept agreed by humans, and if they exist as objects, they can be physical objects with a digital representation, or purely digital ones [143]. Within this broad classification, we have attempted to standardise the entities encountered in the literature review in a consistent manner³⁸.

There are two additional dimensions to the classification that is not currently reflected:

1. There will be specialisation in many cases to accommodate **domain or industry sector** differences (for example, the identifiers and associated metadata for instruments in two scientific domains may not be the same).
2. In some cases, a distinction needs to be made between a **type and an instance of that type**. Scientific instruments again provide a good example - there is an instrument type (make and model) that must be unambiguously identifiable, but there are potentially many instances of the instrument (as reflected by distinct serial numbers). The instances have different or additional characteristics - for example each of them can have one or more calibrations that are unique to an instance, and change over time - leading to **versions** of the instance. These distinct groups: the **class** and the **instance of the class** - may be represented by different PIDs in practice.

The approach for developing a registry of entities entailed developing a broad scope and hierarchy based on observed Entities in our literature review, and then extending this with the terms and stable URIs found in the FABIO, COAR, schema.org, Dublin Core, LoC, and DataCite vocabularies. There will be other classifications to take into account, but time does not allow for a more detailed synthesis. Wherever possible, we use a URI from [WikiData](#) to serve as a common reference in cases where multiple URIs are available for the same concept. Ultimately, we need to be able to reference all entities for which we have knowledge base information on their relationships to persistent identifiers and use cases.

An example of a concept with multiple stable URIs is shown in Table A.2.1.

Table A.2.1 Example of the Variety of Sources for Entity Definitions

Entity	Source	relation	Reference	URL
dataset	WikiData		[56], [59]	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1172284
dataset	FABIO	sameAs	[175]	http://purl.org/spar/fabio/Dataset
Dataset	schema.org	sameAs	[187]	https://schema.org/Dataset
Dataset	LoC	sameAs	[188]	http://id.loc.gov/ontologies/bibframe/Dataset

³⁷ <https://cerif.eurocris.org/vocab/xml/OutputTypes.xml>

³⁸ There is, of course, some ambiguity in respect of ‘abstract things’ - often perceived as physical objects, but they exist as a convention of humans - for example a ‘project’ or an ‘institution’.

dataset	Zenodo	sameAs	[186]	None
dataset	Dublin Core	sameAs	[189]	http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/Dataset

Despite the obvious challenges, the classification will be useful as a mechanism for grouping and classifying PID Stacks and could be considered as an additional facet of service or PID Stack classification in the [Compliance Assessment Toolkit](#) being developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC, and in its attendant Knowledge Base.

Figure A.2.1 Entity classification, with mappings to use case elements (excerpt). [Full version](#).

Having a representative and stable registry of Entity Types assists with the annotation and elaboration of PID services and stacks, and is an important consideration when selecting an appropriate service.

The current classification schema is available [here](#), and is also maintained as a [detailed data \(vocabulary\) table](#).

A.3 Actors and Roles in the Ecosystem

The EOSC PID Policy [35] provides a good starting point for the characterisation of the actors and roles involved in the PID ecosystem - the governance, services, standards, and management required

to ensure, at a minimum, that persistent identifiers are unique and remain resolvable over time³⁹. These interdependent actors and services were reviewed, compared to literature, and refined in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project [66]. We also [review examples of the structure of the ecosystem](#) below and use this as validation for the model.

The current state of our ecosystem model is discussed below and shown in Figure A.3.1, based on a review of several PID services [7], [8], [11], [13], [36], [76], [95], [99], [110].

Figure A.3.1. Actors and roles in the PID ecosystem

1. Many (but not all) **PID Stacks** are based on a published **Scheme** that is governed and maintained by an **Authority**, and is often linked to or based on one or more published **Standards**⁴⁰. In some cases, the **Authority** is designated by the **Standards Body** to manage the **Scheme**. In other cases, an **Authority** may adopt a **Scheme** published by a **Standards Body**.

³⁹ In the interim, the EOSC PID Policy Task Force established Focus Groups to review important topics - including terminology, workflows and actors in the use of PIDs. These resources only became publicly available towards mid 2024, and have only been included partly into the Knowledge Base.

⁴⁰ In reality, many of the standards listed for PID stacks are not yet adopted by a Standards Body - they are often published [RFCs](#) that have not yet been adopted but serve as *de facto* standards [95].

2. An **Authority** serves as the guarantor of identifier uniqueness, and often handles primary resolution duties together with basic kernel metadata. Some **Authorities** provide PID registration, editing, and resolution services directly to the **Owners** and **Users** of the identifiers.
3. In some cases, the **Authority** directly enables a **Provider** to act as local registration and optionally resolution provider, and to optionally extend or manage the kernel metadata schema. Many PID Stacks, however, introduce an additional layer of resolution and/ or uniqueness management between **Providers** and the **Authority (Multi-Provider Agencies or MPAs)**. Such MPAs may also extend the metadata kernel information defined in the **Scheme**.
4. **Providers** (frequently called ‘Services’) enable **Managers** to register PIDs on behalf of **Owners**, and often receive value-added services from the **Provider**. More often than not, **Managers** are repositories of physical and digital materials, or registries of concepts, and several other terms may be used to describe them - e.g. ‘Allocating Agents’ [113].
5. The **Provider** maintains the relation between the referenced entity, the identifier, and the detailed kernel metadata for that object or concept where applicable - usually on behalf of the **Owner** of the object or concept.
6. When **Users** (humans or machines) encounter a PID, resolution is handled by the **Provider** in most cases, but if a PID was issued directly by an **Authority**, resolution is handled by the **Authority**. Sometimes, resolution is cascaded - redirected from a central registry at the **Authority** to a resolution mechanism at the **Provider**.
7. Resolution directs the user either directly to the entity (object) or to its proxy, which is often a (metadata) landing page maintained by the **Manager** on behalf of the **Owner**. In such cases, it is possible to obtain the entity either directly from the **Owner**, or from the **Manager**. This process may not be machine-actionable and may involve manual permission, retrieval, and sharing.

This arrangement leads to a *kernel metadata hierarchy* in some cases, with the simplest arrangement being basic kernel metadata (‘identifier metadata’) lodged directly at the **Authority**, while the most complex arrangement involves kernel metadata at the **Authority**, optionally extended by the **MPA**, and further extended by the **Provider**. **Managers** or **Users** may also keep additional non-kernel metadata about the entity. See A.5 for a more detailed discussion.

A.4 The Concept of PID Stacks

We have referred to PID Stacks a number of times in the document text, and here provide a definition of the concept at the hand of a number of examples and published information on the structure of PID services [2], [17], [26], [36], [67], [91], [95], [110], [111].

PID Stacks are interdependent arrays of actors and roles that serve the end user community (**Owners** and **Users**). Several actors and roles in the ecosystem contribute to more than one PID Stack, and they map onto the model defined in A.3 in various ways. The following sections discuss some of these in detail.

A.4.1 DOI (Digital Object Identifiers)

Digital object identifiers (DOIs) are used widely in the research landscape, primarily to identify research outputs (scholarly publications, datasets, code, and similar). It is also used to identify entities such as samples and specimens [68], data repositories [69], and research-performing institutions [70].

All DOIs are based on unique identifiers and resolution mechanisms provided by the Handle System through the DONA Foundation [7] (**Authority**). The resolution mechanism is based on an open protocol⁴¹ (DO-IRP) [13]. The concept of a digital object that is referenced unambiguously is described in a second protocol (DOIP) [12] (**Scheme**), and this protocol is based on an international **Standard** (X.1255) [71] maintained by DOIP, and registered with the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) (**PID Standards Authority**).

In the case of DOIs, several additional authority-type organisations are present (**Multi-Provider Agencies**) that manage specific schema extensions and portfolios of **Providers**. These Providers offer services based on the extension. There are presently around 10 of these agencies, of which the DOI Foundation [10] is one, and offers DOIs to its **Providers** (in this case referred to as ‘Registration Agencies [10]) based on extensions to the Handle System.

The **Providers**, in turn, offer services to **PID Managers**, usually via some form of membership model that funds the ecosystem operations of the **Manager** as well as the higher-level services in the stack.

There are cases involving additional **Providers** that are offered as virtual services in parallel to a foundational **Provider** service. The best example of this would be DataCite [72], which offers additional services for [RoR](#), [re3Data](#) and [IGSN](#) - but these could also be modelled as niche PID Managers.

Table A.4.1.1 provides a summary of the PID Stack structure for DOI Providers.

Table A.4.1.1 PID Stacks in the Handle Family

Scheme	Authority	MPA	Provider (Registration Agencies)
Handle System	DONA Foundation	Corporation for National Research Initiatives (CNRI)	Not investigated
Handle System	DONA Foundation	Coalition for Handle Services – China	Not investigated
Handle System	DONA Foundation	GDWG/ ePIC	See A.4.6
Handle System	DONA Foundation	CTIC	Not investigated
Handle System	DONA Foundation	MISADI	Not investigated
Handle System	DONA Foundation	Smart Africa Alliance	Not investigated
Handle System	DONA Foundation	Tunisian Internet Alliance	Not investigated
Handle System	DONA Foundation	RosTelecom	Not investigated

⁴¹ The protocol is open since it has been published and it is available for free. But it is not currently possible to participate in the revision process, and it is not possible to find out when and how such revision might be initiated.

Scheme	Authority	MPA	Provider (Registration Agencies)
Handle System	DONA Foundation	Corporation for National Research Initiatives (CNRI)	Not investigated
Handle System	DONA Foundation	Coalition for Handle Services – China	Not investigated
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	Airiti
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	BSI Identify
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	Chinese DOI
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	CNKI
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	CrossRef
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	DataCite
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	EIDR
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	HAND
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	JaLC
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	KISTI
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	mEDRA
Handle System	DONA Foundation	International DOI Foundation	EU-OP

From the table, it is evident that while the majority of research-related PID services are based on a stack including the Handle System, DONA Foundation, and the DOI Foundation via **Providers** such as CrossRef and Datacite, there are many other stacks that are based on actors and components or services in the same family.

The stack is completed by adding **Managers**, of which there can be many (for example, DataCite has 224 members and 56 consortium members at present, and supports in excess of 3000 Managers [73]). DataCite also adds custom **Managers** to its own service (re3Data, IGSN) that act as **Providers** to all intents and purposes, and several of the larger members serve a significant proportion of the community (e.g. Zenodo).

A.4.2 ARK

The Archival Resource Key (ARK) is based on a distributed model, and has a different architecture to DOIs. Both Handle/DOI and ARK provide an open source resolver application, but there is no cost involved with becoming an ARK user.

The basis of uniqueness in ARK rests on the concept of the ‘Name Assigning Authority Number’ (NAAN) registry, which is operated by the California Digital Library on behalf of the ARK Alliance [74]. The Ark Alliance appears not to be particularly formal (i.e. not a membership organisation with defined statutes), but is resourced via voluntary participation in discussion groups based on a code of conduct [75]. Governance is performed by ‘Community Leaders’ and the discussions, meeting agendas, finances, minutes, future plans, and working group activities are openly documented in a wiki [77].

The ARK identifier is based on a **Schema** which is currently under development as an individual contribution in the IETF. The specification is still an Internet Draft, and the intention is to publish it as an Informational RFC [76]. It is not clear when this might happen, since the ARK standardisation process is still unfinished although it started in February 2001. The current draft is number 37, but it is still not compliant with some existing IETF specifications. Note that RFCs with status “Informational” are not Internet standards, so even if ARK specification is published as an RFC, it will not become a standard endorsed by IETF. The main reason for this is that IETF has already approved URN as a standard, and it is IETF policy not to approve two standards for the same purpose. Therefore the **Standards Body** of ARK is the ARK Alliance, not IETF.

Resolution is performed either locally or by a universal service ([N2T](#)), which not only resolves ARKs, but also additional PIDs of use to the community [79] - i.e. a MetaResolver.

All ARKs are registered and resolved by servers that are run and maintained by members of the ARK Alliance. This model is similar to that in other PID systems in one respect: PIDs rely on thousands of institutional web servers that have adopted PIDs, since those servers collectively host the identified resources. ARK resolvers, like URN resolvers, are hosted locally.

Separate from long term access to primary content is long term access to secondary content (PID metadata). In the ARK community, N2T maintains a redundant copy of the ARK metadata outside the institution hosting the primary content. Therefore N2T can act as both a centralised ARK resolver and an external metadata store. It has been available only to a handful of ARK organisations, such as EZID users and the Internet Archive. There are only about 60 million ARKs (records) in N2T, out of 8.2 billion ARKs that have been assigned.

Resource constraints have made it hard to implement an accounting system (access control) for N2T that would permit its more widespread use for ARK organisations. The California Digital Library, which hosts the service, is updating the technology behind N2T. As a part of this process, CDL is investigating a solution for the accounting problem. A new design should enable all ARK organisations to maintain their NAAN registry entries.

The ARK alliance is also looking for a sustainable funding model for N2T. So far the service has been funded mainly by CDL, which may not be able to carry on with it especially if there is a need for all ARK organisations to become N2T users.

The ARK Alliance directly enables a large number of organisations and services to create (mint) ARKs, either by implementing the **Scheme** into their software, or by utilising third-party software to do so. These **Providers** currently number more than a thousand [80], and as a consequence, we provide a few examples in Table A.4.2.1 that may be of interest to the research community involved in EOSC. In relation to the typical actors in the model, the ARK stack does not include **MPAs**.

Table A.4.2.1 Examples of ARK PID Providers in Europe

Scheme	Authority	MPA	Provider (Registration Agencies - a few examples)
N2T	ARK Alliance	Not applicable	Biblioteca Nacional de Portugal (National Library of Portugal)

N2T	ARK Alliance	Not applicable	Centre National d'Études Spatiales (French Space Agency)
N2T	ARK Alliance	Not applicable	Library of the University of Amsterdam
N2T	ARK Alliance	Not applicable	Naturalis Biodiversity Center
N2T	ARK Alliance	Not applicable	Louvre

In Europe, the distribution of ARK Name Assigning Authorities is shown in Figure A.4.2.2. There is a significant concentration in France.

Figure A.4.2.2 Distribution of ARK NAANs in Europe [81].

A.4.3 Contributor Identifiers

A.4.3.1 ISNI

ISNI (International Standard Name Identifier (ISO 27729:2012 [37])) is the ISO standard number for identifying contributors to creative works and those active in their distribution. ISNI covers researchers (for example using ORCID), but also inventors, writers, artists, visual creators, performers, producers, publishers, aggregators, and more. Unlike ORCID, ISNI can be assigned to both natural and legal persons.

The ISNI International Agency Ltd ([ISNI-IA](#)), a limited company registered in the UK, is the Registration **Authority** for the ISNI standard, charged by ISO with governing, promulgating and maintaining the use of ISNI worldwide [155]. ISNI-IA has a governing Board of Directors, including representatives of

some of the original group of Founding Members responsible for launching the standard as well as co-opted or elected members.

ISNI is funded and led by its member organisations. Currently these comprise five Founding Members that are still actively involved, 30 regular Members and more than 35 [Registration Agencies](#) [156] (**Providers**). Registration Agencies are appointed by the ISNI International Agency; they curate and contribute metadata in their own areas of expertise, submit requests for new ISNI assignments and provide ISNI-related services to all users. They are responsible for providing the expert interface between ISNI applicants or other data subjects and the ISNI Assignment Agency (ISNI-AA), which maintains the [ISNI database](#) [156]. [OCLC](#) operates the ISNI-AA on ISNI-IA's behalf.

As of October 2023, approximately 15 million ISNIs have been assigned, of which 1.7 million belong to organisations. There is a cost associated with adding new records to the ISNI database, and ISNI Registration agencies may charge for identifiers.

ISNI identifiers consist of 16 digits, the last one being a checksum based on ISO/IEC 7064:2003. Identifiers are non-semantic; that is, 15 first digits do not have any inherent meaning (unlike e.g. ISBN numbers). Lack of structure maximises the capacity of the system; ISNI will not run out of numbers soon. For the time being, ISNI identifiers are always presented as HTTP URIs. The recommended format is <https://isni.org/isni/<ISNI>>; for instance <https://isni.org/isni/000000012281955X>.

A.4.3.2 ORCID

ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) is a de facto identifier system for researchers, but also a global, not-for-profit organisation sustained by fees from [member organisations](#). ORCID is governed by a [Board of Directors](#) which represents the membership. The identifier is free of charge, and as of December 2024 more than 7.5m ORCIDs have been assigned.

ORCID metadata is provided by researchers themselves and/or harvested from publishers' systems. It describes the roles of researchers as creators of and contributors to research outputs [36]. The identifier is intended to survive changes in researcher affiliation and/or hosting institution, and is well integrated into mainstream research management practice in many countries. There are quality records available in the database, but since minimum requirements are very low (the name and email address) there are also a lot of records which do not identify researchers properly.

Like ISNI, ORCID is based on a global database. Metadata (authority records) are harvested from databases of 85 participating institutions, and merged into union catalogue.

ORCID shares a **Schema** with ISNI⁴². In practice, a block of ISNI numbers has been allocated to ORCID usage. Since ORCID and ISNI are technically identical, it is easy to support them both in an IT system. On the other hand, when not presented as HTTP URI, a lay person cannot separate these identifiers from one another. A user who has an ORCID can use the functionality available in the ORCID system to add ORCID to his ISNI record, and then add the ISNI to ORCID record (see

⁴² As of October 2023, neither ISNI nor ORCID community have registered a URN namespace.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1067-5020>). For the time being it is not possible to launch this unification process from the ISNI database.

A.4.4 URN

Uniform Resource Name (URN) is a distributed system based on independent namespaces such as URN:DOI and [URN:NBN](#). Each URN consists of three parts: the string 'URN:', namespace identifier (NID) such as DOI or NBN, and namespace specific string (NSS). The same NSS may be reused in another namespace, because NIDs are unique.

URN identifiers are based on a **Schema** maintained by the [IETF \(PID Standards Body\)](#) as a **Standard** ([RFC 8141](#)) [32]. URN namespaces are based on a registry maintained by the Internet Assigned Names Authority ([IANA](#)). Each URN namespace has its own **Schema** which may be based on a **Standard**. For instance, [URN:DOI namespace registration](#) is based on the DOI standard (ISO 26324:2022). The Registrant of the namespace becomes the **Authority** of URNs in that namespace. Therefore the URN:DOI namespace authority is the DOI Foundation, but it has no responsibility for URNs in other namespaces.

New namespace registration requests are processed by a group of five experts nominated by IANA. There are currently 70+ namespaces which cover a wide variety of identifier systems and resources, ranging from maritime resources to Austrian governmental publications. Each namespace must have an **Authority**, specified in the registration request.

The URN specification, RFC 8141, is a proposed Internet standard published in 2017. Unlike its predecessor, RFC 2141, it is compliant with the URI syntax (RFC 3986) published in 2005. The URN syntax and character set is specified in RFC 8141 only at a general level. The standard provides a mechanism for sending requests to URN resolvers (R-component) and to target systems (Q-component), but the syntax of the former has not been specified. This work is currently being done in the National Library of Finland, as a part of the project enhancing the functionality of the library's URN resolver.

URN namespace registrations often specify the character set and syntax of the URNs of their respective namespaces in a more restricted manner than RFC 8141. These restrictions may be based on another standard referenced in the namespace registration. For instance, in the URN:ISBN namespace, rules from ISO 2108:2017 International Standard Book Number (ISBN) [19] apply.

However, several URN namespaces are not based on pre-existing identifier standards. Examples of this are URN:NBN (National Bibliography Number) and URN:NAN (National Archive Number). These namespaces, which are administered by the National Library of Finland and the National Archive of Finland, allow national libraries and national archives to use their old in-house identifier systems as persistent identifiers. Since there was no international standard or other documentation describing NBNs, IETF published [RFC 8458](#), 'Using National Bibliography Numbers as Uniform Resource Name' [4]. It is an informational RFC which complements information provided in the [URN:NBN namespace registration](#) [4].

Each URN namespace (e.g NBN, ISBN, etc.) can support multiple **Providers** and **Managers**, each responsible for a set of unique identifiers or a subset of a single identifier system. There are different

ways of achieving this. In the URN:NBN namespace, the first part of every URN:NBN namespace specific string is a country code (e.g. 'URN:NBN:NL' or 'URN:NBN:FI'). This creates national URN:NBN sub-namespaces, which may be divided further, if several organisations assign URN:NBNs in the country.

In an example of the use of URN:NBN, the Dutch Royal Library (KB) serves as one of many URN:NBN Registration Agencies (**Provider**) [142], provides a resolution service (backed by a long-term preservation service), and manages the quality and integrity of identifiers issued by institutional repositories (**Managers**). Other national libraries may serve as registration agencies (see Table A.4.4.1) and provide similar arrangements to local repositories. This leads to a distributed system of identifier management and assignment. In theory, it is overseen by the National Library of Finland (NLF), the registrant of the URN:NBN namespace.

In practice, libraries and other organisations which use URN:NBNs are doing it independently and should consult NLF only if they wish to change the rules of NBN assignment. Such rules, specified in RFC 8458, are very liberal. NBN users may assign these identifiers to basically anything they want, as long as the identifier is actionable (some URN namespaces do not require this and by default do not provide resolution services). A national library may have a wide array of resources which do require persistent identification, from works to manifestations to metadata records describing them, and subject headings in these records.

In the URN:ISBN namespace the rules of URN assignment are dictated by the ISBN standard ([ISO 2108](#)) and related documentation such as [ISBN Users' manual](#), not by RFC 8141. In this namespace, multiplicity of resolution service providers and managers is required and possible because the identifier is semantic. There is no global ISBN database, so URN:ISBNs must be resolved at the national level, for instance in national union catalogues or national bibliography databases. Finding the correct resolver is based on the registration group element (country information) in the identifier. Therefore the URN resolver maintained by NLF can resolve URN:ISBNs with NSS starting 978-951 or 978-952. The National Library of Sweden, for example, will have responsibility for URN:ISBNs where the first digits of the NSS are 978-91.

Note that if some future edition of ISBN is made non-semantic, resolving them as URNs would no longer be possible unless the URI of the correct national resolver is permanently attached to the URN. This will make URN:ISBNs technology dependent, which undermines the persistence of these URNs in the long term. Therefore the organisations using URN:ISBNs have an interest in retaining the current syntax of the identifier. Likewise the URN community has an interest in maintaining the ISSN Portal, the global database containing metadata about all serials which have International Standard Serial Number, or ISSN ([ISO 3297](#)). Without this database URN:ISSNs could not be resolved, because the identifier itself does not contain a hint with respect to where to find the resolver.

There are some features which set URN apart from other PID Stacks:

- URN can encompass all other PIDs as URN namespaces. For the time being, only the URN:DOI namespace has been registered, but Handle.Net already supports URN representation of Handles (as URN:HDL). The URN:DOI namespace is based on ISO 26324

[16] (DOI standard), so these URNs are still DOIs. But they can be extended by RFC 8141 [32] guidelines. Therefore it is not possible to add a URI fragment to DOI, but it is possible to add URN F-component to URN:DOI⁴³.

- Some URN namespaces do not support resolution services⁴⁴. According to RFC 8141 non-actionable URNs are acceptable. The concept of non-actionable PID is unthinkable for all the other PID systems and it does not suit well for e.g. scientific publishing, but it is applicable in many other areas, such as Internet of Things (see [RFC 9039](#)) where the need is only to uniquely identify devices connected to WLANs.
- There will never be a single off-the-shelf URN resolver application for all URN namespaces⁴⁵. URN:DOIs are already supported by the same resolver as normal DOIs, and if a URN namespace is registered for ARK, URN:ARK will use the same resolver as ARKs. Popularity of URN:NBN has suffered from the lack of an open source resolver application, but the National Library of Finland will make its resolver available in GitHub in the near future. This resolver will also support URN:NAN, and an earlier version of it has already been used in the URN:ISSN namespace by the ISSN International Centre for testing purposes.
- Some URN namespaces are themselves distributed. URN:NBN is a good example of this. 13 European countries using URN:NBNs are responsible for their national sub-namespaces, which they are entitled to divide even further.
- Resolving URNs based on non-semantic identifiers such as ISSN (International Standard Serial Number) is possible only if there is a global database which can resolve all URNs in that namespace. Luckily such a database does exist for ISSNs. The problem of finding the correct resolver does not exist for Handle/DOI, because the prefix provides this information. Therefore the suffix (identifier itself) can be non-semantic.
- URN specification and the URN namespace registrations which support resolution services have been written with technology independence in mind. A URN without the resolver URL attached to it is still recognisable as a URN⁴⁶. In this respect URN is similar to ARK, but different from DOI/Handle.

A.4.5 PURL

Persistent URL (PURL) was developed by Stu Weibel and Erik Jul at [OCLC](#) in 1995 [148]. Therefore it predates all other digital PID systems by several years. OCLC never tried to standardise PURL,

⁴³ Note that in URN:DOI URI fragment is called F-component, and it has no role in identification. If a URI fragment is added to a DOI, URI syntax as specified in RFC 3986 is applied, which means that the DOI + URI fragment no longer identifies the entire resource, but the fragment only.

⁴⁴ Neither IETF nor IANA are responsible for collecting statistics about assigned URNs or their use. Such information may be available in some namespaces or sub-sections of namespaces.

⁴⁵ Due to the decentralised nature of the URN system, and the fact that some namespaces do not provide any resolution services, it is impossible to find out which namespaces are actively used, and by whom.

⁴⁶ The URN community hopes to develop with IETF and IANA a mechanism via which the information about URN resolver locations can be found from DNS or systems which will replace it in the future. HTTP will be used as the primary network protocol for a long time, and HTTP-based hyperlinks will probably be supported even longer, but like any other technology, HTTP will disappear at some point in the future.

probably due to the simplicity of the system. There are no PURL identifiers as such. As the name implies, PURLs are just trusted URLs which are redirected to present URLs of identified resources using (initially) a modified HTTP server. If the URL of the resource changes, it can and should be updated. For this purpose an administrative interface tool was created.

Initial PURL implementation was based on the Apache HTTP server. In 2007 OCLC and [Zepheira](#) modernised both the server software and the administrative interface under contract to OCLC. The service was still hosted by OCLC. In September 2016 the resolver service and its administration interface were transferred to the [Internet Archive](#). Applications supporting the service were completely rewritten. Prior to the transfer, the administrative interface of the system had been broken for several months, which meant that broken PURL - URL links could not be fixed and there was no way to mint new PURLs. This was the first time that there were serious sustainability and continuity issues with a PID system. Resolution services [151] are now provided by Internet Archive⁴⁷ [149].

In terms of the PID Ecosystem, PURLs operate without any **Standards, Schema, Provider, or Manager** but the Internet Archive provides resolution services and acts as an **Authority**. **Owners** can register 'domains' as namespaces and create PURLs on demand within that namespace. Owners have no obligation to maintain the link to a resource, and there are no instruments to encourage them to do so. Hence resolution is not managed as closely as with other PID Stacks, and although resolution is built into the architecture, the target of resolution is subject to all of the resolution issues (B.1.3) .

It is important to note that PURLs have had an interruption in persistence in the past, and that there is no explicit sustainability arrangement that will avoid a similar situation in future. Since the Internet Archive uses ARKs as well, PURL may not have strategic importance for it. Compared with other persistent identifier systems PURL is far less popular, and major investments on the development of either PURL specification or its technical infrastructure seem unlikely at the moment. Transfer to the Internet Archive has extended the life time of the system, but in the long term it may be at risk. Hence we assess PURLs as not persistent in a strict sense.

PURLs are used for e.g. identification of [Dublin Core metadata terms](#) and in [COAR vocabularies](#) as identifiers of terms. Therefore PURL is an important system for linked data, and its less than ideal sustainability is a cause for concern.

PURL has been re-invented in the [W3ID community](#) [150]. W3C is not directly involved, but the concept of a persistent URL is aligned with W3C architecture, as long as a fully independent resolver application is not needed.

A.4.6 ePIC

DONA (the **Authority**) operates the [Global Handle Registry](#) (GHR) for the Handle system, and enables a portfolio of **Multi-Primary Administrators** to provide PID services based on Handles [91], [111]. The current portfolio includes the Corporation for National Research Initiatives (CNRI), the Chinese

⁴⁷ The service hosted on Internet Archive servers supports access via [purl.org](#), [purl.net](#), [purl.info](#), and [purl.com](#).

Handle Coalition (CHC), International DOI Foundation (IDF), Communications and Information Technology Commission (CITC), Smart Africa Alliance, MISAVA Agency for Digital Identifiers (MISADI), and the Gesellschaft für Wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen (GWDG) on behalf of ePIC Consortium.

ePIC uses the Handle **Schema** as a primary definition of kernel metadata, and allows extensions of this via Data Type Registry entries - which can include, for example, Dublin Core metadata. Individual institutions can become members of the ePIC consortium, and these institutions each receive a unique prefix within the Handle system. The members act as **Providers** and assist **Managers** and **Owners** with allocation of PIDs for their resources [111].

The ePIC stack is similar to the DOI stack in respect of actors and roles, since the ePIC Consortium acts to all intents and purposes as an **MPA**.

Table A.4.6.1 Registration Agencies in the ePIC Consortium [111]

Scheme	Authority	MPA	Provider (Registration Agencies)
Handle System	DONA Foundation	GDWG/ ePIC	CLARIN
Handle System	DONA Foundation	GDWG/ ePIC	CNIC
Handle System	DONA Foundation	GDWG/ ePIC	CSC
Handle System	DONA Foundation	GDWG/ ePIC	CSCS
Handle System	DONA Foundation	GDWG/ ePIC	DKRZ
Handle System	DONA Foundation	GDWG/ ePIC	GRNET
Handle System	DONA Foundation	GDWG/ ePIC	GWDG
Handle System	DONA Foundation	GDWG/ ePIC	SND
Handle System	DONA Foundation	GDWG/ ePIC	SURE

The ePIC Consortium is strongly active in EOSC [11] and is expected to play a role in future PID services for EOSC.

In addition to the stacks discussed in detail in the preceding sections, a large number of PID Stacks have been documented in the Knowledge Base - see [Annexure G](#).

Annexure B: Elements, Features, and Attributes of PID Stacks

It is clear from review of literature that there are a wide-ranging number of features, attributes, and characteristics that the community expects from PID services [2], [5], [6], [11], [28]. In addition, PID services, authorities, and schemes often advertise or emphasise their benefits and distinguishing features [2].

This annexure provides a broad classification of such characteristics, features, and attributes in eight categories. In most cases, these will also have sub-categories. Each PID Stack can be mapped onto these categories, helping us to record the characteristics and features of each. We discuss some foundational elements of PID Stacks in detail, and provide a summary of others that have been identified. We also explicitly indicate best practices as and where they are apparent from literature.

These, in turn, can be linked to PID use cases or workflows and its elements - allowing a selection of the PIDs best suited to a specific use case element based on its features.

The elements, features, and attributes of PID Stacks contribute to a [Knowledge Graph](#) based on the Information Model ([Figure A.1.1](#))

B.1 Primary Functions of PIDs

Permanent access to the identified resource or its surrogate is only one service persistent identifiers can provide. All PIDs rely on resolver applications, which may support a set of services using metadata stored either in the resolver itself, or systems the resolver is aware of or redirects to. While the range of these services has so far been limited, it is desirable that future resolver services are extended, and that the PID systems themselves specify the features with which service requests can be embedded to identifiers. The first attempt to specify PID resolution services was made by IETF almost 25 years ago in [RFC 2483](#) [198] (URI Resolution Services Necessary for URN Resolution). Since then, other PID systems have specified their own services. There has been little or no cooperation in this area between PID systems⁴⁸.

Moreover, the set of services specified in RFC 2483 reflects the state of the art of digital asset management systems in use in the late 1990s. It has become necessary to support a wider variety of services, since now we have for instance digital archives, which contain technical and archival metadata about resources preserved in the long term. A user may request for instance technical metadata about a resource to see what hardware and software she will need in order to render the resource.

As long as resolution services are perceived as functionally similar to HTTP (with persistence added), true benefits of using PIDs in linked data are not fully exploited. Moreover, users may see PID resolution as an extra step - a perception to be avoided.

International standard identifiers, such as ISBN and ISSN, have been widely used since the early 1970s in libraries and in the field of research and scholarly publication [95]. These identifiers predate

⁴⁸ These aspects are revisited in our gap analysis (Annexure G) and in the recommendations.

the widespread use of digital publication of research outputs by more than two decades. The first services that focused on digital persistent identifiers emerged in the late 1990s⁴⁹ [95], [96], [138]. However, it took a while before PID services and especially DOI became popular - it would be difficult to think of scientific publishing without DOI services. It is worth noting that the earliest adoption of a community-endorsed standard coding for concepts was developed as far back as 1893 - the forerunner of what is now known as the ICD (International Classification of Diseases), administered by WHO [199]. Work on standardising disease descriptions started far earlier, though, with initial publications around 50 years prior.

Basic requirement for both traditional identifiers and PIDs is the same: an identifier, once it has been assigned to a resource, must not be assigned to another resource. However, we may specify some additional requirements for PIDs. The first attempt to do this was done in [RFC 1737](#) [200] (“Functional Requirements for Uniform Resource Names”). In spite of the title, these requirements may potentially be applied to all PIDs that are based on URNs:

- **Global scope:** A PID is a name with global scope which does not imply a location. It has the same meaning everywhere.
- **Global uniqueness:** The same PID will never be assigned to two different resources.
- **Persistence:** It is intended that the lifetime of a PID be permanent. That is, the URN will be globally unique forever, and may well be used as a reference to a resource well beyond the lifetime of the resource it identifies or of any naming authority involved in the assignment of its name.
- **Scalability:** PIDs can be assigned to any resource that might conceivably be available on the network, for hundreds of years.
- **Legacy support:** The scheme must permit the support of existing legacy naming systems, insofar as they satisfy the other requirements described here. For example, ISBN numbers, ISO public identifiers, and UPC product codes seem to satisfy the functional requirements, and allow an embedding that satisfies the syntactic requirements described here.
- **Extensibility:** Any scheme for PIDs must permit future extensions to the scheme.
- **Independence:** It is solely the responsibility of a name issuing authority to determine the conditions under which it will issue a name.
- **Resolution:** A PID will not impede resolution (e.g. translation into a URL for HTTP resolution). To be more specific, for PIDs that have corresponding URLs, there must be some feasible mechanism to translate a URN to a URL.

⁴⁹ Handle, 1994; Persistent URL (PURL), 1995; Uniform Resource Name (URN), 1997; Archival resource keys (ARK), 2001; Extensible resource identifier (XRI), 2005 [95]

B.1.1 GUPRI

It is fair to say that the main functionality expected from persistent identifiers in the community is threefold: it must unambiguously and **uniquely identify** an object or concept, it must be **persistent**, and it must be **resolvable** (actionable in the internet) [95]. To this, one can add a nuance: that the uniqueness and resolvability must apply **globally**, at least within a formally defined namespace [65]. This can be summarised as a primary composite expectation: ‘GUPRI - Globally Unique, Persistent, Resolvable Identifiers’ [65].

Some persistent identifiers, e.g. PURL or GRID, have poor sustainability prospects, and may not remain resolvable or persistent

Figure B.1.1.1: Globally Unique, Persistent and Resolvable Identifiers [0], [65]

These primary functions are shown in Figure B.1.1.1, presented to indicate that a complete overlap is not in evidence for all the PID Stacks that we have reviewed: as an example, URNs are globally unique within a namespace, they are persistent⁵⁰, they are most certainly identifiers, but they lack a common and standardised resolution mechanism on the web [95]. As such, they are not easily resolvable. The same is true of many of the URIs associated with controlled vocabularies. Likewise, the vast majority of public URLs on the web are globally unique identifiers and are resolvable, but they are far from persistent. Some identifiers, such as PURLs, have poor sustainability prospects and may not remain resolvable or persistent. Others, such as VIAF or RRID:AddGene, are short serial numbers that are locally unique, and cannot be used as an identifier without context, for example by adding a CURIE [201]. In detailed matching of PID Stacks with features, we will make these distinctions where applicable, and it is an important feature of the Knowledge Base.

⁵⁰ See the next section for a detailed discussion of persistence.

B.1.2 Persistence

It has been said that persistence implies that ‘an identifier is available for long enough’ [95], and informally, most end users of PIDs equate persistence with near-indefinite availability [11] of both the PID [102] and the resource that it identifies and resolves to - something that is clearly not universally feasible, and in practice does not happen for several reasons [5], [6], [88], [99], [154], [187].

So - what is meant by persistence? What are the features expected of persistence? The following are some of the expectations of persistence that we could identify:

1. Persistent identifiers should only be assigned to resources that will be preserved for long term, that is, over several hardware and software generations [11], [95];
2. A persistent identifier and the services it provides should be at least as persistent as the resource identified [95], [112] - but this does not support the use case for academic citation [101], [141].
3. The resource may undergo several migrations and previous versions may become unavailable or difficult to obtain and/or render. Users relying on PIDs of outdated versions of documents should be made aware of the latest version available, with metadata, a landing page, or similar, which may enable acquisition of the work in some other form [95], or indicate reasons for unavailability [99], [103], [107], [112], [141].
4. Note that some users may want to retrieve the original and authentic (non-migrated) version of a resource, and they may have special tools with which to render the outdated file format. Therefore automatic redirection to the most modern version should not always be the default behaviour, especially if the user has requested a specific manifestation (version/representation) PID.

In guaranteeing or supporting persistence, there are several additional considerations:

1. Most pertinent is that [persistence relies on effort](#) [1], [99], [138], [141]. Without such effort, persistence breaks down, and there are very few, if any, technical solutions that can mitigate this issue [97], [99], [102], [104]. In essence, it requires non-technical measures (policies, sustainability and succession planning, agreements, capacity building, best practices, and the like) to mitigate the situation. One can identify three components to this effort requirement [141], and it usually involves multiple actors in any given PID Stack:
 - a. **Registry and Resolution Persistence:** this requires the operator(s) of identifier registries, resolution mechanism(s) and its supporting infrastructure to be available for a long time;
 - b. **Management Persistence:** maintaining the correct link between the identifier and the resolution target is generally the responsibility of the Manager; and
 - c. **Resource Persistence:** the resource referenced by the identifier must also remain accessible and usable, subject to version management strategies, and, sometimes, legal constraints.

2. Persistence is not binary - web content exhibits a range of persistence behaviour [88], [98], and PID systems intend to improve the persistence of resources that would otherwise be less so. Some scholarly content, for example, has a half-life of approximately 9-10 years on the web [100]. Moreover, the half-life for each PID Stack is determined by the length of time such PID Stacks have been available - those that have been in operation longer will inevitably have a different half-life than services that started recently.

Within well-established PID Stacks, consortia are formed or members often collaborate to provide mutual mirroring and redundancy of services, and/ or to guarantee continuity should a node become unavailable [112].

B.1.3 Resolution: Some Complexity

One would expect that PID Stacks would offer a fairly standardised and predictable approach to resolution, but this is not the case. The following can be summarised from resolution practices:

1. **One-to-Many:** A single resource on the web does not have a one-to-one relationship with a PID that resolves to it in all cases [95]. The same resource can be referenced by more than one PID [6], [95]. For example, the following PIDs both resolve to the same resource:
 - a. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1105.3459v1>
 - b. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1105.3459>
2. **Multi-step/ cascading resolution:** The Handle System is a good example of this. It offers a single-step resolution process for native Handles registered directly in the system, but it also functions as a primary resolution mechanism for (amongst others) the DOI and ePIC PID Stacks, redirecting resolution requests to the secondary or even tertiary resolvers operated for these schemes [8], [10], [91], [95].
3. **Re-allocation and versions:** Not all persistent identifiers maintain versioning of the resource it references in the same way, and in some cases, the PID resolves to the latest version of the resource. This is sometimes problematic, for example if a history of a resource is the objective of study, the historical versions of the resource cannot be referenced unambiguously via a PID since the PID resolves to the latest version only [95], [99]. One way of solving this problem is to resolve PIDs of works to landing pages, which contain links to all versions.
4. **Multiple Locations and Manifestations:** it is somewhat common for the exact same resource (for example a dataset or article) to be located at more than one location in the web, but a PID will resolve to only one location in the web. Moreover, some resources are the same expression (work), but have multiple manifestations⁵¹, an issue that could be addressed through **multiple resolution** if the manifestations are all digital (see next item). Additional PIDs may be created for additional copies without any restriction [95]. For instance, a publisher may assign a DOI for an article it publishes, but a copy of the article in an

⁵¹ Manifestation refers to the situation where, for example, a digital resource has a printed equivalent, of which there can be many.

institutional repository receives a Handle, and a legal deposit copy archived by the national library may get a URN:NBN. Note that while the publisher identifies works, the national library identifies *manifestations* of that work. If the article is available in several formats, they all share the same DOI, but each one has its own URN:NBN. Manifestation level identification is essential for e.g. long term preservation.

5. **Multiple Resolution:** HTTP supports multiple resolution via the 300 status code, and this is implemented by some PID Stacks to enable resolution to multiple *representations* or possibly *manifestations* of the same digital content. This could be a combination of a typical slate: a human-readable landing page with metadata and other information, a machine-readable metadata representation, a direct link to the digital object being described, and a link to a long-term preservation copy.
6. **Content Drift:** It is common for poorly curated resources to have a change in content over time, although the PID that resolves to the resource remains stable. This is problematic from a scientific reproducibility point of view, since citations of the resource made in the past may not reference the exact content used to derive new results any longer [6], [98], [108]. This ‘fixity’ of the resource is especially important for data and code. In some cases, however, drift is expected and acceptable - for example in Wikipedia pages.
7. **Resolution Channels:** there is at least one study [88] that confirms a worrying phenomenon - that resolution success depends on authentication status (even for open access resources) and on the HTTP request method.
8. **Link Rot:** if a PID is not properly administered, URL the PID resolves to may cease to function (HTTP 404 error) or provide a default error page indicating the same (this is an extreme case of content drift), in which case HTTP may not be aware of the problem [1]. Moreover, providing a tombstone page⁵² for a resource that is no longer available technically resolves properly, but the content is not what is expected.
9. **Tagging and Compact Identifiers:** In some cases, there are use cases and emerging best practices in respect of using compact identifiers, for example in manuscripts [153]. The resolution behaviour is not standardised, and resolution is thus not guaranteed.

These issues, amongst others, are handled better by some PID schemes and stacks, but also require non-technical responses (policy, capacity building, best practices) to ensure fitness for use. The aspects of mitigation and service quality are addressed in [Annexure E](#).

B.1.4 Unique Identification

Identifiers for resources (which may or may not be web-based or digital) lie at the root of the development of persistent identifiers, and predates the digital age [95]. Several interrelated concerns need to be noted (graphical representation in Figure B.1.4.1):

⁵² Tombstone pages serve as a persistent landing page - usually containing metadata - for resources that had to be removed. Once published, scholarly outputs should not be retracted or destroyed, except in cases of legal requirements (requiring destruction after a period of time), or research fraud.

Figure B.1.4.1 Identifiers and Resolvers [0]

1. The **Identifier** consists of an **Identity String** [99] that is guaranteed to be unique, optionally within a **Namespace**⁵³. Many of the schemata conventions and standards applicable to PID Stacks deal with how these are constructed, and how they guarantee uniqueness [95]. Some schemata optionally defines check digits to also guarantee accuracy. It is strongly discouraged to embed semantic meaning into these identifier strings [141], but in some cases (for example in PIDs based on Handle System) this is a specification in the scheme.
2. There are cases where the **Identifier** is reused in its entirety as an **Identity String** in a different PID Stack. It is entirely possible to take an identifier (e.g. arXiv.1105.3459 in the arXiv scheme) and reuse it within a different scheme (e.g. 10.48550/arXiv.1105.3459 in the DOI scheme). In such a case, both these Identifiers resolve to the same resource [6].
3. **Identifiers** can be wrapped, prefixed, and otherwise parsed into HTTP strings that are resolvable directly in a web browser (**HTTP Pattern**) [76]. Again, using the examples above, to dereference the **Identifier** via the ArXiv service will result in one **HTTP Pattern** being applied to obtain a **Resolvable String** (<https://arxiv.org/abs/1105.3459v1>), while doing so for the DOI service will result in a different one (<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1105.3459>).
4. **Compact Identifiers** are used extensively to reference concepts, and there is a need to provide resolution support for these [123], [147], [153].

⁵³ Namespaces are not managed by PID Stacks in a uniform way. Approaches include centralised namespace control (for example ARK or DOI-based stacks), hierarchical control (for example URN:NBN), to a fully open and flat mechanism (as with PURLs).

5. **Identifiers** can also be dereferenced by directly passing them to a **Resolver** for the applicable PID Stack/ Scheme. The [Knowledge Base](#) provides a comprehensive inventory of these.
6. **Metaresolvers** [79], [102], [123] can also be used to resolve an **Identifier**, and in most cases works on the principle that it recognises the schema from the structure of the Identifier, applies the appropriate **HTTP Pattern**, and redirects to the appropriate **Resolver**, or without applying the appropriate pattern, retrieves a dereferenced URL to the resource from the **Resolver** API and returns that to the requester.
7. Finally, the Object or Service referenced by the **Identifier** can in itself just be an additional **Identifier** in a different context (or even the Identity String in principle). For example, a file path/ name can be an identity string, or a hash can be computed based on the referenced object to serve as an identity string [119], [164].

Identifiers can be used to reference many different entities, and it is important to select a PID Stack appropriate to the type of entity [11]. In addition, unambiguous identification of versions is important in some contexts (see B.1.5), and it is also sometimes necessary to identify fragments of the resource.

B.1.5 Content Variance

User expectations in respect of content variance is not a single concept, although there is often a perception that the resource referenced by a PID should ‘remain unchanged forever’. There are several complementary considerations here:

1. The range of content variations that are generically applicable to content in the web [0], [99] - these include⁵⁴
 - a. **No Change**: content remains unchanged down to bit-level, as evidenced by e.g. a checksum;
 - b. **Schematic Changes/ Transformation**: content is amended (format transformations) for preservation, size⁵⁵, or fitness-for-use. For scientific reproducibility to be supported, such transformations must be reversible to checksum-level and provenance made available.
 - c. **Improvements**: Usually performed by the owner of a resource or by curators on behalf of the owner, and involves metadata completeness, structuring of resources, etc. It may also include corrections to erroneous data (for example due to calibration errors).you
 - d. **Semantic Enhancements**: Improvements to resources - for example through semantic linking and alignment with disciplinary norms, named entity recognition, adding linked open data references, and similar actions.

⁵⁴ These items correspond more or less one-to-one with a vocabulary developed in [99], but have been renamed and described somewhat differently.

⁵⁵ For example by lossless compression.

- e. **Content Growth:** Dynamically growing resources (such as observation databases). For these cases, several best practices have been published [99], [104].
2. There are several approaches to and policies in respect of versioning, which map to the items above depending on the intentions and policies of the PID Provider and/ or Manager [99], [103].
3. These usually involve a trigger for deciding on when to generate a new version and depends on the policy implemented by the PID Provider and/ or Manager, and these triggers can be calculated on a number of different bases [0]:
 - a. **Checksum-based:** any change to the resource (in total or a component of a resource) that results in a checksum change triggers a new identifier [118];
 - b. **Reproducibility-based:** If the same derived results cannot be obtained from the altered resource (in an academic context), a new identifier is required [0];
 - c. **Heuristic-based:** Rules are defined for curators to determine whether a new identifier is required, with or without assistance of the other two methods.
4. It is common for curators to make amendments to resources that do not trigger major version changes (for example creating a long-term preservation copy of a data file in a different format, or improving metadata), but when they do, a major version with a new identifier, including provenance information to link the versions, is a good practice [103], [109].
5. A useful test in respect of format transformations would be to evaluate reversibility: if a format change is reversible and reverse-transformed copy yields the same checksum result as the original, a new version is not required, provided that the provenance and means to effect transformations are documented [0].
6. Some datasets are routinely updated dynamically, and usually incrementally, in such a way that complicates assigning an identifier to the entire dataset (its content is not stable, and the granularity is too coarse for proper citation), but it is often too large - and likely to be subsetted frequently - to support finer granularity for identifiers. Some best practices have been published [104] and were supported by community consensus in RDA [109].
7. Versioning semantics may be aligned with good practice in respect of software versioning [171], adapted as follows: Given a version number MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH, increment the:
 - a. MAJOR version when you make changes that do not support reproducibility;
 - b. MINOR version when you add content in a reproducibility-compatible manner
 - c. PATCH version when you make backward compatible improvements

B.1.6 Metadata

There are potentially multiple sets of metadata associated with any identifier, and the scope of metadata is dependent on the PID Stack. In Table B.1.6.1.1, we indicate the scope of metadata at the

hand of examples. Metadata also depends on the Entity being referenced, and in many cases are dependent on the research domain or the type of an Entity.

A distinction is made between **Kernel Metadata** and **Custom Metadata**:

1. **Kernel Metadata**: offered by the formalised system that manages the PID Stack, and standardised or based on well-publicised and managed schema in most (but not all) cases [26], [78], [114]. Kernel metadata also functionally has two distinct parts, although these are sometimes made available in a single schema:
 - a. **Identifier Metadata**: typically information about the account that created the identifier, date of creation and/ or modification, and the original or current redirection URL(s) that are linked to the identifier (e.g. [26], [42], [114]). This metadata is maintained by the resolution service (which may be chained or federated in some cases).
 - b. **Resource Metadata**: typically standardised and offered by the Provider, describes the resource in formal metadata terms, dealing with aspects of citation, coverage, subject and keywords, rights and licensing, and more. It is important to note that the resource metadata often only reflects the latest version, and that not all PID Stacks have standardised metadata schema [78], [96].
 - c. In the definition of FAIR Digital Objects [145], it is envisaged that this metadata be extended to assist with resolution options and its actionability. Other mechanisms exist to achieve similar ends without extending kernel metadata, e.g. ARK inflections [29], [105] or Signposting [105].
2. **Custom Metadata**: The metadata presented as a landing page or most common target of resolution. These are generally provided by the Manager or the Owner of the resource in addition to 1(b), and should in almost all cases be the authoritative version of the metadata (See B.1.6.2). It is often aligned with or based on domain or format-specific schemata, and offers significant diversity. Managers often retain older versions of the metadata and provenance information about changes and versioning [103], [109]. The Custom Metadata typically either extends the Kernel Metadata, or maps to it.

B.1.6.1 Metadata Scope

Table B.1.6.1.1 Scope of metadata associated with PID Stacks (examples)

PID Stack	Authority	MPA	Provider	Manager	Owner
<i>Kernel</i>	<i>Kernel Metadata</i>			<i>Custom (Resource) Metadata</i>	
Handle System	Handle Metadata	N/A	N/A	N/A	Optional
DataCite DOI	Handle Metadata	IDF Metadata	DataCite	Manager ⁵⁶	Optional
IGSN DOI	Handle Metadata	IDF Metadata	IGSN	Manager ⁵⁷	Optional
ARK	ARK Metadata	N/A	Optional		Optional
URN:NBN	N/A	N/A	Optional	Optional	Optional
ORCID	ORCID Metadata	N/A	N/A	Optional	N/A
ePIC	Handle Metadata	ePIC Metadata	Optional	N/A	Optional

Authoritative copies: grey: resource/ custom metadata, blue: identifier/ kernel metadata

B.1.6.2 Authoritative Metadata

As indicated above, the Custom Metadata is often the authoritative version, and it is managed in a decentralised way by Owners and Managers. Initiatives such as FDO promote moving some Custom Metadata higher up in the resolution chain (including it in Kernel Metadata)[145], [146]. There are advantages and disadvantages to both approaches:

1. **Custom Metadata at the point of resolution:** this will usually be the Authority or MPA in the PID Stack.
 - a. **Advantages**
 - i. There are fewer redirects required to obtain the metadata *if PID resolution is the primary means of access*. However, a sizable proportion of redirects to scholarly content originates from web search and direct links to content or metadata, and for these, the benefit does not apply.
 - ii. Obtaining the metadata is highly probable, if not guaranteed.
 - iii. All the custom metadata records for a PID Service can be found at a single source.
 - b. **Disadvantages**
 - i. It requires extra work for the Managers and Providers to maintain synchronisation between their versions and those of the resolution point.

⁵⁶ Custom extensions of the mandatory DataCite schema, managed by repositories (e.g. DANS, Zenodo, PANGAEA, etc.)

⁵⁷ Custom extensions of the mandatory IGSN schema, managed by repositories (e.g. ARDC, GeoScience Australia, GEOMAR, etc.)

- ii. The point of resolution will have to store a much larger volume of data, and while metadata records are small, some PID Stacks involve hundreds of millions (or even billions) of records and might encounter scalability issues.
 - iii. Decentralised management and control of the metadata content and the means to reference it provides protection to the community in respect of monopolistic practices and abuse of power (provided minimum sustainability provisions are in place).
 - iv. The authoritative version should be hosted where curation and quality assurance is performed (i.e. the Manager and/ or Provider). Authorities have little or no capacity or ability to curate content.
 - v. It is highly unlikely that all Authorities and MPAs could be persuaded to host additional metadata, leading to increased diversity of workflows for developers and users of PIDs.
 - vi. Custom metadata schemata vary considerably between Managers and Providers for sound reasons (format and domain diversity). Because of this diversity, presenting such metadata to humans in a readable form will be very challenging.
 - vii. The centralised resolution points are unlikely to add custom value to metadata (for example acting in domain- or community-specific ways on machine-readable links in the metadata, or providing community-specific links to value-addition tools).
2. **Custom Metadata managed at the target of resolution:** This will usually be a landing page or resource curated by a Manager.
- a. **Advantages**
 - i. Having Managers provide authoritative metadata has many advantages, including partial or full mitigation of the disadvantages listed above.
 - ii. The relationship between owners (depositors) and Managers is important and trust (through quality assurance, curation, and guidance) is cemented by designating Managers as custodians of authoritative metadata.
 - iii. Specialisation in terms of custom metadata and metadata guidance is very difficult to provide at scale. Managers usually deal with smaller and well-defined collections.
 - b. **Disadvantages**
 - i. Aggregation of metadata in the same domain, if spread over multiple Managers, requires harvesting to a central catalogue or federated search that is costly and complex, even though it is common practice.

Best practice in our view would be to focus on the Manager and/ or Provider for authoritative metadata in all cases where this is possible and applicable, and extend Kernel Metadata for administrative content that is currently not available (See Annexure F).

B.1.6.2 Extensions to Custom Metadata: Other Alternatives

The objective of simplifying access to custom metadata by extending kernel metadata can be achieved in other ways that are inherently more flexible and extensible. Four recent developments can assist with this:

1. **Signposting:** Signposting simplifies machine actionability of scholarly content in the web by extending these objects with standardised **Typed Links** [105], [106]. Typed links can be provided in HTTP **Link Headers**, HTML **Link Elements**, and **Link Sets**. The typed links can point to any or all resources associated with the object - such as the PID, object type, metadata, landing pages, authors, and many more.
2. **Reproducibility and RO-Crate:** RO-Crate standardises the description of research context for reproducibility purposes, allowing references to inputs, outputs, code, methodologies, platforms, instruments, and the like [62] using a metadata schema [63].
3. **Research Context and RAiD:** Developed by the ARDC, RAiD aims to describe a research activity - which can be long-running and transcend multiple projects simultaneously or over time [136]. It does so in a standardised way [137], and provides a persistent identifier to aggregate linked open data references to relevant resources: projects, grants, institutions, researchers, samples, outputs, and similar.
4. **FAIR Digital Object Framework (FDOF):** The framework [145] proposes a specification for implementing FAIR Digital Objects [146] by standardising important attributes (location of custom metadata, object type) as part of the identifier metadata.

B.1.7 Other Functionality Considerations

Additional functionality aspects are discussed here.

- **Scalability and Extensibility:** It is desirable for PID Stacks to be scalable (grow significantly in terms of volume) [11], [28] and to be extensible (grow in respect of scope of services and features) [16], [28].
- **Independence:** this consideration covers a range of technical concerns, including
 - Protocol independence: it is important for identifiers not to rely on the HTTP protocol for its uniqueness and structure [28], [95];
 - Platform independence: allowing a single reference to provide multiple representations of the same content [16];
 - Encoding: specifying case-insensitive and UTF-8 encoded identifiers ensures maximum resilience [28]. In a special case, ARK identifiers are case sensitive to allow for more compact strings [2], [78].

B.2 Service Topology

Service topology deals with the manner in which PID Stacks provide resolution, redundancy, and service continuity. In broad terms, there are several options for these:

1. **Central Resolution:** One resolution point is provided for all of the identifiers in a PID Stack. Examples include ARK [79], ORCID [120], ArXiv [90], SWHID [119], and the Handle System [8].
2. **Cascading Resolution:** PID Stacks that rely on the Handle System for primary resolution are examples of this: ePIC [112] and all DOI-based stacks [26]. For some instances of ARK, forwarding for secondary resolution is also done [82].
3. **Decentralised Resolution:** Decentralised resolution can be performed by any node in a distributed ledger arrangement (similar to Blockchain) [83], [122]. Emerging stacks such as DiD [121] are based on this topology.
4. **Network Resolution:** One of the ePIC partners, GWDG, runs a Global Handle Registry Mirror, hence the resolution is assured in Europe even if other parts of the global network are temporarily not available [91].
5. **Independent Resolution:** The URN:NBN [95] identifier is a good example: each allocation agent (having the role of Provider) offers its own resolution endpoint - for example, in the Netherlands the service is hosted by DANS on behalf of the Royal Library [9].

Network resolution, as described above, provides redundancy, but the other topologies require specific arrangements to achieve it (See 'Service Levels' below). Likewise, service continuity - both in terms of temporary and permanent unavailability of a Provider, Manager, or Authority - has to be arranged (see 'Governance' below).

B.3 Cost Recovery

All PID services, whether these are free to the Owner, end user, or Manager, cost money to operate and maintain. Various cost recovery (revenue) models are in evidence to sustain PID Stacks, and these are described in Table B.3.1 at the hand of example PID Stacks.

Moreover, services can be based on a profit motive (commercial services) or be offered by non-profit organisations based on cost recovery and contingency [27], [99]. Some services appear to be 'free' across all aspects of the PID Stack, but in reality the costs are sponsored, hidden, or cross-subsidised.

In any event, some end user costs (such as resolution of an identifier) are always free, access to the content or resource metadata is mostly free [27], and Owner costs (registration of an identifier) is largely free, depending on the fee structure of the PID Manager. Access to the resource itself depends on the Owner - access to articles published in subscription journals will, for example, not be free.

Table B.3.1 Cost Recovery Models - Examples

Model	Stack	Authority	Resolution	MPA Costs	Provider	Manager	Owner
Free ⁵⁸	Handle	N/A	N/A	-> Authority	-> MPA	N/A	Free
	ARK	Cross-subsidised		N/A	-> Authority		Free
Hidden	DiD	Costs covered by nodes				Free	Free
Membership	ePIC	Authority		-> Authority	-> MPA	-> Provider	Free
Mixed ⁵⁹	Datacite DOI	Authority		-> Authority	-> MPA	-> Provider	Free ⁶⁰
Volume ⁶¹	CrossRef DOI	Authority		-> Authority	-> MPA	-> Provider	Free ¹¹
Sponsored	ORCID	Covered by sponsor		N/A	Sponsor	Free	Free
Subsidised	ARK	Authority		N/A	-> Authority or Free		Free
Pay-per-Use	ISMN	Authority		N/A	-> Authority		-> Provider

Cost models are:

- **Free:** unlikely to be really free, but the costs are recovered by different means from some revenue source in the ecosystem (see ‘Subsidised’ and ‘Sponsored’). The Handle System and ARK for example, provides free registration of PIDs directly by Owners, but the costs are borne by formal participants in the PID Stack.
- **Hidden:** the costs of use are not explicitly defined. Decentralised identifiers such as DiD would be an example: registry duties and resolution can be performed by any node in the distributed ledger network, and the costs are borne by the nodes on behalf of the beneficiaries. Should all nodes withdraw due to cost considerations, there is no clear continuity plan.
- **Membership:** The membership model is common, and suits situations where PID stacks are focused on service based on true costs. ePIC partners (Providers within an MPA managed by GDWG) contribute the costs of maintaining contributions to the DONA Foundation for resolution services, and cover the costs of providing services to associated Managers.
- **Volume:** These models recover costs from Managers based on volume of PIDs registered, and uses this revenue to fund the other actors in the stack - in the case of Crossref, which is

⁵⁸ The Handle system and ARK, when used directly by an Owner, are free - but in reality, subsidised by the fee-based part of the service

⁵⁹ Membership fee plus some volume-based recovery, membership includes a tranche of included PIDs.

⁶⁰ There are exceptions to this, since PID Managers minting DOIs, for example, are allowed to recover a fee from Owners.

⁶¹ CrossRef has [membership fees](#), but this does not cover PID registration - [billed separately based on volume](#).

volume-based - to fund the MPA (DOI Foundation), which in turn transfers revenue to the DONA Foundation for maintenance of the schema, master registry, and resolution services.

- **Mixed:** A combination of membership and volume-based revenue, as practised by DataCite.
- **Sponsored:** The cost of membership or volume costs are borne by a sponsor on behalf of PID Managers - for example funding organisations sponsoring the costs of ORCID on behalf of research-performing institutions.
- **Subsidised:** Owners can mint ARK identifiers directly without any costs, for example - these costs are covered by revenue obtained from Managers and Providers.
- **Pay-per-Use:** some services, for example the International Standard Music Number (ISMN) [202], require owners of works to pay for each registration - for example for each recording of a song.

There is a significant additional consideration here: *fee-for-service arrangements are likely to be more sustainable*, with a much clearer definition of the responsibilities and obligations of actors in the ecosystem than services that are 'free'. Best practice will be to select PID stacks where cost recovery is explicit.

B.4 Performance

These features deal with best practices and expectations of the community that are not technical, but describe the performance characteristics of the PID Stack. Features include Governance, Sustainability, Value Addition, and Service Levels.

A number of governance and sustainability-related expectations and best practices are proposed by [POSI](#) [27] (Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure), a consensus based on contributions from a number of prominent PID Providers and Authorities⁶². These are confirmed and extended by literature review.

B.4.1 Governance

Governance should be open and transparent, and community-focused.

1. **Coverage:** the expectation is that infrastructure (PID Stacks) should transcend disciplines, geography, institutions and stakeholders [11], [27], [82] - and this is mostly the case except for identifiers dealing with domain-specific concepts [123], [124]. The user community requires an ecosystem of PID Infrastructures to support a wide variety of scientific applications and offers sufficient flexibility (service providers, scheme, attribute set) [35].

⁶² POSI is endorsed by a [growing number of organisations](#).

2. **Stakeholder Involvement:** the community served by the infrastructure should contribute to governance [11] - usually this is done by community and/or member representation on a governing board [26],[27].
3. **Open Membership:** Membership must be open to all on a non-discriminatory, opt-in basis [27], [82].
4. **Transparent:** activities related to member representation and election to governing structures should be transparent with a view to building trust [27], [82]. In some cases, all operational and strategic documentation - including finances - are publicly available [77]. Transparency should be constrained by privacy and other legal obligations [27]. Transparency should extend to refraining from lobbying for regulatory change - this must happen via the community [27].
5. **Continuity:** Public trust depends on clarity in respect of continuity measures. POSI calls for a 'Living Will', that "publicly describes a plan addressing the condition under which an organisation would be wound down, how this would happen, and how any ongoing assets could be archived and preserved when passed to a successor organisation" [27]. Continuity plans are a common requirement for PID infrastructure [35], [99], and for example repository infrastructure [125].
6. **Formal incentives:** It is possible that the function provided by public infrastructure becomes obsolete due to technological or societal change. In such a case, it must be clear that the organisation has achieved its mission and that operations will be wound down [27], [82].

B.4.1 Sustainability

Sustainability is achieved through a number of arrangements. These include financial sustainability and technical sustainability - 'insurance'.

1. Financial sustainability

- a. **Sustainable operational revenue:** this is an obvious cornerstone of sustainability - the ability to sustain operations from revenue [27]. Revenue sources might include value-added services, consulting, API Service Level Agreements or membership fees [26], [27].
- b. **Mission-consistent:** Revenue should be consistent with the mission - and not run counter to the objectives of the organisation [27].
- c. **Differentiation:** Structural income (service fee-based revenue) should fund operations, while time-limited funding (e.g. projects) must be used for non-operational activities [27].

- d. **Surplus:** generating a surplus beyond operational cost is a necessity to deal with economic, social and technological change [27].
 - e. **Contingency:** In addition to the above it is recommended to provision for at least 12 months of operations in case of a managed wind-down [27].
2. **Technical sustainability:** technical sustainability or insurance can be improved through a number of measures.
- a. **Open Source:** all code to operate the infrastructure services must be open source [27]. Software to run the organisation is excluded.
 - b. **Open Data:** All identifier data and metadata should be made available under an open licence [27].
 - c. **Accessible:** Open data provides legal, but not practical access - frequent data dumps should be published [27].
 - d. **No Patents:** “The organisation should commit to a patent non-assertion covenant. The organisation may obtain patents to protect its own operations, but not use them to prevent the community from replicating the infrastructure” [27].

B.4.3 Value Addition

Value Addition is achieved through two broad mechanisms: providing advice and guidance to the community and by enhancing basic resolution and metadata services.

1. **Community Advice:** The majority of PID Stacks (usually Providers) offer substantial guidance documentation that is freely available [109], [120], [126].
2. **Services**
 - a. **Metrics:** Some examples are discussed below.
 - i. **Crossref** [129] provides extensive metadata and citation information for scholarly content, along with usage statistics and citation counts through services such as Event Data and Cited-by.
 - ii. **DataCite** [128] offers usage and citation metrics for research data through its DataCite Event Data service. It tracks data usage, citations, and provides insights to data publishers.
 - iii. **ORCID** [127] provides various metrics and statistics to users, including profile views, works accessed, and other information related to the use of ORCID IDs for researcher identification.

- iv. **Scholix** [130] integrates PID information from Crossref, DataCite, ORCID, and OpenAIRE, and provides metrics data via [Scholexplorer](#).
- b. **APIs and Integration:** Many PID Stacks offer APIs for direct integration of their services into other infrastructures. Such integration is not always limited to the resource itself: ORCID, for example, can also be used for authentication via API integration [120].
- c. **Data Typing:** This could be offered as an additional service by associating or linking specific data or metadata with an external identifier (LOD Services). This enables users to retrieve and access structured information related to the resource [29].
- d. **Multiple Resolution:** in the context of persistent identifiers, such as DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers), this refers to the capability of a persistent identifier to be resolved to multiple locations or representations of the digital object it identifies [29]. This means that a single persistent identifier, such as a DOI, can point to different versions or copies of the same resource or provide access to the same content through various means. The motivation for this includes:
 - i. **Content Versions:** Digital objects may have multiple versions, such as preprints, published versions, translations, or different file formats.
 - ii. **Redundancy and Backup:** If one location is temporarily unavailable or if a resource is moved, users can still access the content through alternative resolutions.
 - iii. **Mirroring:** Persistent identifiers can be used to enable geographic mirroring. For example, a PID may resolve to servers in different regions, improving access speed and redundancy.
 - iv. **Customisation:** Managers use multiple resolution to customise user experience.
 - v. **Context:** PIDs can be resolved to provide additional metadata and context about the digital object, allowing citation and linking to related resources.

B.4.4 Service Levels

Service level expectations include obligations and duties of actors in the ecosystem in respect of administration and information/ service integrity.

- **Administrative Capacity:** it is fairly common for Authorities and/ or MPAs to develop policies, and optionally enter into agreements with Providers to ensure minimum standards of quality of administration [26]. Furthermore, Providers may also enter into agreements with Managers, and develop policies with a similar aim [112], [132].

- **Competence:** Authorities and/ or MPAs may require tests or assessments to determine the competence of a Provider [26], [112]. In some cases, formal certification may be required.
 - **Unambiguous allocation:** The responsibility of ensuring that identifiers are unique mostly lies with Managers (allocation agents, registration agencies). Systems must be in place to guarantee this [26], [112].
 - **Interoperability Guarantee:** It is a requirement that Managers operate infrastructure in such a way that interoperability with other Managers is guaranteed [26].
 - **Record-keeping:** All Managers must have adequate record keeping in respect of identifiers [26], [112], which should include date of allocation of a DOI name, and the identity of the registrant on whose behalf the DOI name was allocated [26].
 - **Monitoring:** Managers and Providers may be required to monitor the use of services and to report on this [112], while Authorities or MPAs usually do the same [127], [128].
- **Information and Service Integrity**
 - **Redundancy:** Authorities, MPAs, Managers, and Providers must all have adequate provisioning for data preservation: archiving, mirroring, and backup procedures aligned with typical best practices in this regard (for example ISO 27001) [61], [74], [132], [133], [135].
 - **Incident Management:** While not explicitly stated in many cases, it is reasonable to expect that Authorities, MPAs, Managers, and Providers must have adequate incident management infrastructure in place: threat detection and mitigation, availability and platform usage monitoring, helpdesk facilities, and similar [112].
 - **Availability:** It is generally expected that resolution services and resolution targets will be available 24/7 [35], [112] given the fact that a large number of research infrastructures rely on identifier services for operation.
 - **Authenticity:** PIDs should not be re-assigned or deleted. In case that the entity being identified is deleted or ceases to exist, tombstone information needs to be available in one way or another [35], [107],[112],[132].
 - **Integrity:** The integrity of the system depends on all elements in a PID Stack honouring their obligations, but ultimately Owners are responsible for maintenance of the resource metadata and other linked information about the resource [35], [112]. This process is assisted by ensuring that identifier management is restricted to a particular agent [28].

- **Quality Assurance:** It is critical for Owners to maintain metadata as necessitated by changes to the resource, and for Managers to verify and propagate these changes as required by the PID Stack characteristics, and to design and implement specific operational processes quality control of input data and output data. [26], [132], [133].
- **Certification:** users need to trust PID services [11], and certification may confirm competence in respect of some or all of the above performance attributes [99], [112], [135].

B.5 Definition

A minimum amount of metadata is required of each participant in a PID Stack. In addition to the relationships defined in A.1, we have identified a set of important attributes from literature - especially by reviewing the type of information required and recorded by metaresolvers [79], [102], [123], [135]. These aspects are discussed in [Annexure G](#).

Annexure C: Use Cases and Workflows

C.1 Benefits Expected from PID Use

The main reason for conceiving identifiers that are persistent is an attempt to alleviate the effects of changes in the location or availability of web resources [134]. This is a pervasive problem even in seemingly well-managed scholarly environments, and has been well documented [28],[95],[99],[100] and to some extent analysed [6],[88],[98].

In the research environment, the direct consequences of so-called 'link rot' include lack of accurate citation, poor reproducibility, additional work for all involved in the research cycle, and a gradual loss of research outputs that are made available as digital assets [134]. Persistent identifiers mitigate these issues, and also bring additional benefits that are not linked to the primary aim of improving the persistence of web resources.

Figure C.1.1. Main Benefits of Persistent Identifiers based on Literature Review

We have developed a categorisation of these benefits based on published work, and these are discussed below. The main categories identified here are supplemented by detailed individual benefit statements that can be incorporated into the [Knowledge Base](#) in time.

1. **Efficiency:** the most commonly identified benefit (Figure C.1.1), it is aimed at reducing the administrative, collation, and verification burden placed on researchers, funders, research managers, infrastructure providers, and research performing organisations during the course of many workflows that they engage in [52], [56], [61].

2. **Precision:** Persistent identifiers assist with more precise citation and attribution, more accurate metadata about co-authors, affiliations, and funding, improved tracing of data sources for scientific results with suitable granularity, improved reporting and assessment, and increased interoperability of data [52], [58], [61].
3. **Automation:** As both scientific, service, and administrative workflows become increasingly automated, identifiers will play an increasingly important role to allow such automation to be executed with a minimum of error [52], [60], [61]. It is a direct objective of FAIR to improve machine actionability through the use of persistent identifiers [139].
4. **Federation:** federation of services of various types become simpler using persistent identifiers - including linked open data-based contextualisation of resources [52].
5. **Aggregation:** At the various scales, aggregating information about entities and the relationships between them enables strategic analysis, benchmarking, monitoring, and evaluation [60], [61]. The emergence of PID Graphs and Scientific Knowledge Graphs will depend increasingly on precise referencing via persistent identifiers [140].

C.2 Stakeholders in the PID Landscape

The stakeholder community involved in the use of PIDs, and in its direct and indirect benefits is equivalent to the academic or public research enterprise and its stakeholders [47], [61]. A registry of Stakeholder Types has been developed based on occurrences and references in use cases, and this serves as a starting point for annotating the Knowledge Base with use cases and expected benefits of applying PIDs, and which stakeholders are expected to benefit.

Figure C.2.1. Typical Stakeholders based on Literature Review

We distinguish two superclasses of Stakeholder Types: *Organisations or Institutions* (e.g. Libraries or Funders), and *Groups of Individuals* with the same interests or requirements (e.g. Researchers or Data Stewards).

An important consideration is that some stakeholders benefit **directly** from the use of PIDs (for example researchers or repositories), while some benefit **indirectly** (e.g. research performing organisations, or funders).

Figure C.2.2 represents data that were collected by FAIR-IMPACT through community survey [160], indicating that the majority of respondents are subject to PID policies derived from the service providers, and that especially national policies are not common as a source of PID quality assurance.

Figure C.2.2.2 - Source of PID Policy by Stakeholder Group [160]

More data needs to be collected on this aspect, covering a wider range of stakeholders and regions (FAIR-IMPACT focuses on Europe).

C.3 Use Cases and Workflows

Based in literature review, largely comprised of national PID strategies developed in RDA [65], [66], [67], [68], [69], [70], [71], [72], [73], [74], [88], [96], a number of use cases and workflows were identified. The terminology used to describe the use cases and the associated workflows were standardised, and grouped where appropriate to further improve the usability of the data that were reported.

Figure C.3.1 and Table C.3.2 provide a summary view of the scope of use cases and workflows identified, inclusive of the proposed classifications that will be used in the Knowledge Base to characterise demand. This categorisation is used to elaborate the information model:

- We identify a number of **Workflow Categories** that attempt to cover the scope of PID-related activities in the research landscape.
- These Workflow Categories apply to **Use Cases**, and a Use Case can be applicable in more than one Workflow Category.
- Use Cases are linked to **Benefits**, which in turn serves as the **Business Case** for implementing a specific PID service.
- The Workflow Categories broadly cover the scope of typical Current Research Information Systems (CRISs) implemented at many research-performing and funding institutions, and as such should use terminology from [CERIF](#)⁶³ as appropriate.
- The Workflow Categories are also interlinked, with Use Cases in one category linking to or following on those in another.

Information Model

High-Level Workflow Categories

Figure C.3.1: Information Model, and Workflow Categories proposed in the Knowledge Base

Future national, network, or institutional PID strategies and policies can benefit from structured reporting of benefits, use cases, and workflows. The proposed categorisations and vocabularies created in the Knowledge Base will be shared via the RDA WG on National PID Strategies⁶⁴ for future use and adoption.

⁶³ <https://eurocris.org/services/main-features-cerif>

⁶⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-wg/activity/>

Table C.3.2: Examples of Data Gathered In Respect of Relations between Use Cases, Workflows, and Benefits

Use Case or Workflow	Workflow Category	Description	Benefits
Acknowledgement and citation of works	Citation and Attribution	...assigned DOIs (associated with evolving collections of data) must be used in research papers to properly give credit to each of the modeling groups providing the data.	1) Appropriate citation and attribution
Grant review processes	Grant Application Processes	"Funding agencies and universities also stand to benefit from efficiencies gained by automatic information exchange between systems."	1) Reduced administrative overhead for institutions/funders 2) Less manual data entry 3) More accurate data 4) Time/effort savings for researchers
Institutional research management workflow	Reporting, Monitoring, and Evaluation Processes	"PIDs infrastructure promises much more accurate and timely reporting for key metrics including the number of publications produced at an institution in a given year, the total number of grants, and the amount of grant funding received."	1) More timely data for reporting and analysis 2) More accurate data
Registering and reporting research	Contextualisation and Compliance Processes	"They can also much more easily see whether researchers have met mandated obligations for open access publishing and open data sharing."	1) Reduced administrative overhead for institutions/funders 2) Time/effort savings for researchers
Improved SKG Information	Value Addition and Reuse	"Ultimately the knowledge graph will permit a much clearer understanding of global research networks, research impact, and the ways in which knowledge is created in a highly interconnected world."	
Tracking data sources for reproducibility and scientific integrity	Value Addition and Reuse	Although the DOIs assigned to relatively large aggregations of datasets are well suited for citation and acknowledgment purposes, they are not issued at fine enough granularity to meet the scientific imperative that published results should be traceable and verifiable.	1) Tracing of data sources for scientific results with suitable granularity

C.4 Entities Referenced by PIDs

There is surprisingly little information available about the **Entities** referenced by **Identifiers** beyond the recommendations made by the PID Providers on possible use of the PIDs they offer. In many cases, end users are faced with choices, and one would hope that information about use and recommendations about best practices would be available to assist with these choices.

At the present time, the information available for matching Entities to PID services was compiled as follows, based on a collection of ‘Case Studies’:

1. Each of the ‘**National Strategies**’ collected by the RDA Working Group [65], [66], [67], [68], [69], [70], [71], [72], [73], [74], [88], [96] mostly contain either a confirmation of use of specific identifiers for specific applications and entities, a recommendation to do so, or an intention to promote its use in future.
2. Where applicable, we have included information from review articles that recommend or confirm the use of specific identifiers for referencing an entity in a community of practice. In all, four such ‘**Community Recommendations**’ were included.
3. Two ‘**Community Survey**’ results are also available, and these were included in the Knowledge Base.
4. In some instances, Provider web resources indicate the entities that are best suited for being referenced by the identifier they offer, or their kernel metadata schema includes a vocabulary for specifying an Entity being described, or both. In all, we process 13 such ‘**Provider Recommendations**’.
5. For those identifiers lacking explicit links to entities, an AI-supported retrieval was also processed, afterwards verified by human curators. We executed 123 such ‘**Verified AI Recommendations**’, confirming the typical entities referenced by each Identifier.

Figure C.4.1 provides a summary of the most common matches for the top 10 identifiers.

Three additional sources of information have not yet been included into the Knowledge Base, and it is planned to do so for the next release. These are:

1. In the **re3Data registry**, repositories can optionally record the PID systems that they use, and they can also optionally record the entities that they accept data for [557]. This information can be harvested via the re3data API [247], and we have done so. However, there is no explicit link between the specific identifier in use for a specific entity, and hence a heuristic will have to be devised to refine this information.
2. The FAIRCORE4EOSC project has developed **surveys** for Managers and Providers in which we explicitly ask for identifiers to be linked to entities, and these responses, if enough are received, will provide the most reliable information.
3. To date, **data policies** that mandate or recommend the use of specific identifiers for specific entities have not been reviewed at all. If time and resources allow, we will attempt to

retrieve such information via **named entity recognition** applied to a corpus of data policies, typically focusing on EOSC-relevant sources such as those published by ERICs.

Most Common Identifiers and Most Referenced Entities

Figure C.4.1 Most Common Identifiers and Most Referenced Entities in Case Studies

Annexure D: Matching Supply and Demand

The sections below detail the scope of information that is being used to match supply and demand of PID services in the Knowledge Base. Many of these characteristics, especially for providers, are not readily available from web resources⁶⁵, and are currently provided from validated AI-generated content. The ongoing survey process, indicated below, will gradually replace this information with details curated by the manager or provider in question.

D.1 Assessment of Fitness for Use

The scope of information gathered here, and refined via surveys of Managers and Owners, is intended to determine the characteristics that end users look for in PID Services.

The list below defines the survey content in more detail for each of the entities being referenced.

1. Entity being referenced
2. Positioning in the PID Stack (actors and roles involved)
3. Identifier selected for the Entity
4. Workflows involved and expected benefits from PID use
5. Global resolution - what type of resolution service is required?
 - a. HTTP Resolution
 - b. Resolver page
 - c. API Resolution
6. Resolution target: what are your expectations in terms of the target of resolution and any options that may be available?
7. How will versioning be managed? Can content referenced by the same PID change over time?
8. Human readability [97], [153] - is this a requirement?
9. Namespaces - will a dedicated namespace or prefix be required?
10. Defined metadata [97] - is there a need for a kernel metadata schema to be available?
11. Entity-specific metadata - is this required, or will it be provided by the Manager/ Repository?
12. Sustainability, persistence commitment policies [97], [99] - is this an important consideration?

⁶⁵ 'Not readily available': Information may be available but it was not possible to find and confirm the information with resources available in the project.

13. What capacity can you provide to manage PID resolvability and information security, and what do you expect other actors in the ecosystem to contribute?
14. Value-added services - which of these are needed? This includes Metrics, Content Negotiation [154], and API and Harvesting Services.
15. Scale and costs
 - a. Cost recovery mechanism - is it acceptable to pay for the service?
 - b. Scalability - total number and annual level of use required
 - c. If PIDs are required at scale, will acting as a Provider be considered?
16. International Standard
17. Use Case
18. Life Cycle [97]
19. EOSC PID Policy Compliance

The [current survey form](#) is available for responses at the time of writing.

D.2 Assessment of Service Offering

Likewise, a survey will supplement the information currently available for the Provider community. The scope of information requested in the survey is summarised below:

1. Indication of the Identifiers (PID Stacks) supported by the service, and the position of the service in the PID Ecosystem.
2. Which entities can be referenced by the identifier(s) provided?
3. Description of the other actors involved in the PID stacks(s) in question.
4. The identifier and its characteristics:
 - a. The standards and standards bodies (if any) applicable to the Identifier.
 - b. Namespace(s): how are namespaces managed?
 - c. Identifier registries: how and where are identifiers managed and preserved?
 - d. Identifier Pattern: if the identifier pattern is standardised, please provide a regular expression that can be used to match it
 - e. Human readable: are the identifiers easily readable and processable by humans?
5. Characteristics of the resolution mechanism for the PID Stack.
 - a. Point of resolution - is it centralised, federated, or distributed, and which actors in the stack are involved?
 - b. Resolution - what type of resolution service is provided?

- c. Are there options available in resolution (e.g multiple resolution, content negotiation, ...)
 - d. Information about resolution endpoints, patterns, and APIs as applicable.
- 6. Metadata options offered:
 - a. Identifier and kernel metadata, differentiation based on entity, and support for additional custom metadata.
 - b. Standardisation, of any, of the metadata schema.
 - c. Where is metadata hosted in the stack?
- 7. Sustainability: information on social sustainability and governance, technical sustainability, and financial arrangements and cost recovery. Endorsement of POSI.
- 8. Scalability: how scalable is the service?
- 9. Service levels and capacity, and certification in respect of trust and/ or information security.

The [survey form](#) is currently open for responses.

Annexure E: Ensuring Quality of Service

This discussion deals with options available to the community to improve and ensure quality of service in the ID ecosystem. It forms the basis of a collection of best practices and recommendations that will be included into the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) via the Knowledge Base.

E.1 Quality Assurance Options Available to the Community

The extensive analysis of the characteristics, features, and attributes of Identifier services presented in the preceding sections (Annexures A, B, and C) serves both as a high-level organisation and source of best practices and implementation recommendations (collectively: guidance). Below, we present a synopsis of the scope of guidance to be deployed in the Knowledge Base in Release 2.

Many of the topics covered below are also included in the EOSC PID Policy [35]. To some extent, those that are not are candidates for future extension of the policy, since it may be one of the only mechanisms available

E.1.1 Governance-Focused

#	Aspect	Description of Guidance and Best practice	References
E.1.1.1	Governance	These measures include the establishment of both provider and community governance mechanisms. Providers need to involve the community in its governance structures, and the community, including end users, owners, managers, providers and authorities will benefit from collective advisory, if not governance, arrangements. There is a significant number of additional good practices identified - including coverage-, transparency and openness-, and focus-related aspects.	[11], [26] [27], [35] [77], [82]
E.1.1.2	Sustainability	Sustainability includes aspects of social sustainability (continuity planning, transparency, certification, and trust), financial sustainability (nature of income, contingency, surpluses), and technical sustainability - the latter deals with measures to ensure that the information assets of the service are not lost if it needs to cease operations.	[11], [27], [35], [77], [82], [99], [112], [152]
E.1.1.3	Cost Recovery and Business Model	Emerging PID services often neglect to consider the establishment of a sustainable cost recovery and business model as early as possible. There are many examples, these have been standardised in the Knowledge Base in terms of cost recovery types or options. POSI provides high-level best practices in this regard, and it should be noted that non-profit services are generally trusted more by the	[2], [26], [35], [38], [99]

		research community ⁶⁶ . Costs need to be justifiable and transparent in the case of non-profit services.	
E.1.1.4	Rules of Engagement or Participation, Certification	No specific recommendations or guidance (yet), but in principle, compliance with some or all of PID policy provisions can be made a condition of participation in a network or infrastructure, for example EOSC or an EOSC Node.	[11], [35], [99], [112], [192]
E.1.1.5	Publicly Available Information	This includes transparent publication of persistence commitments and policies, and making information on important performance metrics (especially persistence and resolvability) available to the community.	[35], [99], [102]
E.1.1.6	Policy Scope	Institutions involved in Identifier Management can improve the quality of PID use by defining appropriate policy provisions in respect of versioning strategy, content withdrawal and/ or removal, and the responsibilities of the Owner and the Manager in respect of metadata maintenance. A PID identifier scheme should be selected that supports the versioning strategy.	[35], [99], [103], [104], [107]

E.1.2 Technology-Focused

#	Aspect	Description	References
	Standards and Specifications	Standards and specifications could improve aspects such as kernel metadata interoperability and automation, standardisation of identifier metadata schemata, and of actions/ methods available from authority registries. All metadata (identifier, kernel, and custom metadata) could be modified by or on behalf of the Owner, and methods to do so should be standardised. Work is needed to develop and promote standard exchange of kernel metadata between registration agencies, and to ensure that custom metadata is authoritative and includes all mandatory kernel metadata elements. There are at least two approaches to the improvement of machine actionability and readability of the metadata associated with a PID - centralisation (as exemplified by FDO) and distributed decentralisation (as in Signposting). Reasoned advice on best practices is required.	[16], [26], [28], [35], [114], [144]

⁶⁶ We have not found any specific research results on this topic, but widespread adoption of public services, and funder or institutional policies that exclude or discourage commercial service use seem to confirm this.

	Systems, Tools, and Services	The quality of service is improved through provision of machine-actionable services, including resolution infrastructure, content negotiation, multiple resolution, data APIs and data dumps. Mechanisms for capture and validation of kernel metadata ensure that minimum metadata is provided, and that it is schema-compliant. Service availability, integrity, and security need to be managed and meet community expectations. Services are provided at TRL9, or TRL8 for beta releases.	[26], [29], [35], [112], [195]
	Vocabularies and Registries	Maintenance of a set of terms (concepts and terms, or a glossary) has started via the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, but this is an ongoing task for community curation in future.	[0]
	Technology Independence	Protocols that are platform- and protocol-independent (i.e do not rely on HTTP only for resolution, or on DNS only for uniqueness) are inherently more robust and protected against future change, and is an important consideration for emerging PID services	[16], [28], [95]
	Resolution Topology	Resolver services can be centralised, or decentralised (federated, cascading, or independent). Each approach has advantages and disadvantages, but federated or cascading resolver services support redundancy and utility better than centralised or distributed systems. Distributed systems can be mediated via metaresolvers.	[26], [32], [79], [102]

E.1.3 Performance-Focused

#	Aspect	Description	References
	Fitness for Use	End users may require extensible and scalable services.	[11], [16], [28]
	Community Benchmarks	At present, there are no community benchmarks in respect of performance expected from the suppliers of persistent identifiers, and a mechanism to determine these is clearly required. It may be possible to propose default benchmarks based on best practices, but these serve as placeholders.	[0]
	Defined Responsibility	One of the most important considerations, and one adequately addressed in the structured EOSC PID Policy version as derived by FAIRCORE4EOSC, is to clearly define the roles and responsibilities of actors in	[35], [66], [141]

		the ecosystem, since their adequate performance is required in concert to guarantee service quality.	
	Information and Service Integrity	Management and ownership of an identifier must be restricted to a single party, and adequate security, redundancy, integrity, and failover provisions need to be in place. Encryption must be used in cases where it is needed. Resolution integrity, uniqueness, and versioning management are additional factors that contribute service integrity. Incident management needs to be in place to address physical and digital issues and threats.	[28], [35], [61], [112],[132], [133]
	Resolution Performance and Features	Resolution is expected to be efficient, have near continuous availability, and to remain operational for a long period of time. Moreover, for many identifier services, utility is improved by offering differentiated resolution pathways, through mechanisms such as content negotiation and multiple resolution. Machine actionability of resolution targets can further be extended and enhanced through mechanisms such as Signposting for object-level metadata, and by FAIRiCAT for collection, registry, and repository metadata. FDO also aims to make additional features (richer metadata, additional actions) available at the resolver.	[16], [35], [61], [88], [106], [154], [191], [193], [194]
	Human-focused Performance Features	These considerations include measures by Providers to offer human readable identifiers when the application requires them, Managers ensuring that tombstone pages are available for deprecated or withdrawn content,	[99], [35], [107], [112], [132]

E.1.4 Capacity-Focused

#	Aspect	Description	References
	Reference Implementations, Templates and Examples	<p>Deployable code for implementation of resolver endpoints and registries are sometimes made available, as are code examples in using APIs and templates for metadata records.</p> <p>The community would benefit from templates, examples, and code for UIs in respect of validated metadata capture, and in resolution applications. It is likely that thousands of Managers have developed UI code for metadata capture, leading to variations in quality and wasted resources. Additionally, metadata crosswalks are duplicated</p>	[104], [107], [109], [126],

		regularly, and the FAIRCORE4EOSC MSCR ⁶⁷ component will address this. The Knowledge Base could be extended in future to link to these resources.	
	Training and Support Materials	Providers and Managers can improve the quality of metadata associated with PIDs, resolvability, and the appropriate use of their services by making guidance and best practices freely available.	[26], [35], [132], [133]
	Adequate Service Provision Capacity	This ensures that administration of services and record-keeping are performed at an adequate level, that unambiguous allocation is not in doubt. Monitoring that adequate capacity is available is recommended.	[26], [35], [112]
	Training and Capacity Building Events		
	Identifier Selection Support	Support that enables prospective users of PIDs to select an appropriate service on the basis of many considerations, including scalability, entity specificity, spatial and domain coverage, and many more. This ensures that PID services are applied properly. The PID Knowledge base is specifically available to address this aspect.	[11], [28], [29], [30], [32], [35], [61], [86]

E.2 Roles and Responsibilities

A functional and quality-assured PID Ecosystem requires that many stakeholders and actors in the system each perform at a minimum level of maturity, and to some extent, this can be achieved by

E.3 Classification of Guidance and Best Practices

The OSTRails project has started analysis and evaluation of the scope of guidance that is typical of FAIR Assessment tools used by the community, and this result can be generalised to other applications that rely on structured guidance, best practices, and recommendations. The information model in development in OSTRails is shown in Figure E.3.1.

The utility of this model is found in the improved ability to tag and classify instances of guidance, best practices, and recommendations, and to explicitly link them to standards, focus areas, compliance assessment elements (criteria, principles, metrics, benchmarks and tests), and to

⁶⁷ [FAIRCORE4EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalks Registry.](https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr)
<https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

cross-cutting classes such as communities, domains, and 'networks'. These 'networks' refer to any kind of multi-organisation arrangement - such as the EOSC Federation and its nodes, ERICs, international and regional networks such as RDA, World Data System, and similar.

Each of these linking and classification perspectives require one of the following formalisations:

1. A vocabulary, which can be
 - a. An external vocabulary that is used in full or in part to identify concepts;
 - b. A hybrid of one or more external vocabularies, optionally supplemented by concepts that are not included anywhere; and
 - c. Fully new vocabulary.
2. A registry, which can again be any of the three types defined for vocabulary - external, hybrid, or local.

Figure E.3.1 An Information Model for Guidance, Best Practices, and Recommendations

These vocabularies and registries will possibly be developed further in the OSTrails project, and in the interim, the CAT Knowledge Base will define local and hybrid vocabularies and registries with a view to possibly migrating and and/ or refactoring them in future.

Annexure F: Gap Analysis

This discussion deals with gaps identified during the review and analysis activities reported in this document. Some of these gaps and concerns were also identified in the recently submitted deliverable D2.3 (FAIRCORE4EOSC), currently under review by the European Commission.

1. Governance and Policy:

- a. **Scope:** Existing policies, for example the EOSC PID Policy, do not fully cover characteristics and features expected by the end user community, and may require extension as a result.
 - b. **Assessment and Compliance Mandate:** Moreover, such policies lack mandates and assessment or verification authorities at the present time.
 - c. **Vocabularies:** A number of vocabularies and registries are required for proper operation of the PID appraisal and assessment platforms developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC, and its associated Knowledge Base developed in collaboration with FAIR-IMPACT, but community structures to own, maintain, and extend these semantic resources are not in place.
 - d. **Engagement Mandate:** There is no mechanism for the EOSC-related community, currently informally represented by Opportunity Area 1, to engage meaningfully and with an adequate mandate with the supply ecosystem (Providers, Authorities, mostly) with a view to extension and harmonisation of PID services.
 - e. **National, Network, and Institutional Policies:** No explicit *PID policies* could be found. Such policy provisions (in respect of PID use) are often contained in other policies (especially the case for Managers - e.g. repositories, and networks such as ERICs). The RDA has developed a portfolio of national strategies, and while this is a good starting point, these efforts fall short of identifying and harmonising the use of PIDs in research data production, where it is critical for true interoperability and AI-readiness. The Compliance Assessment Toolkit helps to address some of the deficiency by simplifying the creation of a national, network, or institutional policy.
2. **Features:** Not all PID services exhibit a common, interoperable set of features that will be required to assess the quality of service from an end user perspective. This aspect links to some extent to the performance gaps and harmonisation requirements discussed below, since some commonly implemented features are required to properly assess performance.
 3. **Performance Metric Gaps:** There are numerous performance gaps that were identified, but perhaps the most important of these involve the two critical characteristics of PIDs: persistence and resolvability. For neither of these, consistent and verified public evidence is available across the PID services.
 4. **Benchmarks:** At present, there are *no community benchmarks* in respect of performance expected from the suppliers of persistent identifiers, and a mechanism to determine and

maintain these is clearly required. The FAIRCORE4EOSC project, during implementation of the CAT, has proposed a set of default benchmarks that require community ownership and validation.

5. **Harmonisation:** Harmonisation⁶⁸ is required in respect of the machine actions and content offered in Kernel Metadata, as follows:
 - a. **Identifier Metadata:** identifier metadata (i.e. always available through a request to the authoritative registry of a PID service) must include administrative metadata that is used *inter alia* to determine important metrics in respect of PID services.
 - b. **Actions:** extension and harmonisation of PID service actions that can be requested from individual PIDs (e.g. consistent content negotiation implementation) and from registries (e.g. offering random samples of PIDs) are required.
 - c. **Competing Approaches:** there are at least two approaches to the improvement of machine actionability and readability of the metadata associated with a PID - centralisation (as exemplified by FDO) and distributed decentralisation (as in Signposting) [144]. Reasoned advice on best practices is required.
6. **Poor Practices:** There are several instances of these, including
 - a. **Resolution Variance:** there are documented cases of resolution success depending on access methods (for example, authenticated users resolving a PID successfully but non-authenticated users do not). There may be cases where this variance is desirable, but for resolution to a metadata landing page, it is not good practice.
 - b. **Absence of Continuity Arrangements:** In a few documented cases, PID services ceased to exist, or were interrupted for significant periods of time due to poor or nonexistent continuity arrangements. These persistent identifiers are either now not resolvable, or the future sustainability of the current services are in doubt. We will attempt to assess the extent of continuity planning in future releases of the Knowledge Base.
7. **Capacity Building, Support Materials:** There is generally no single mechanism to obtain training, training materials, and supporting resources across a wide variety of PID services.
 - a. **Reference Implementations, Templates and Examples:** These are typically difficult to find from a single source. The Knowledge Base could be extended in future to link to these resources, since it can be integrated into the guidance information that is made available (see E.3)
 - b. **Training Courses for PID Actors:** a consideration would be to develop courses that are integrated with the PID Knowledge Base, accounting for stakeholder groups - funders and policy makers, end users, data stewards and curators, and developers.

⁶⁸ FAIRCORE4EOSC has made some proposals in this regard, and it will be included into work done jointly by FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT in respect of Kernel Information Profiles. Also see B.1.6.1.

Annexure G: Knowledge Base

G.1 Context

The PID Knowledge Base (KB), a joint effort between FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT, and incorporating many of the knowledge aspects that were identified and structured in this document, has been published independently [197]. The Knowledge Base will be updated from time to time, and the latest and authoritative version will be available in Zenodo⁶⁹ after publication of this document.

The Knowledge Base supports a number of use cases:

1. Within the FAIRCORE4EOSC CAT, the KB serves as the basis for the selection and guidance function to end users, allowing them to select and understand the nature of PID services available to them.
2. In addition, PID services that have completed an assessment in CAT can be found on the basis of compliance and performance in respect of individual metrics and the aggregate assessment.
3. It allows Monitoring Services being developed for CAT in FAIRCORE4EOSC to retrieve the composition of PID stacks. This is required to compute aggregate test results at higher levels in the stack hierarchy from tests performed at the level of Providers and Managers.

G.2 Specification of Minimum Content

Based on the discussion in Annexure E.1, the following minimum specifications of content for the Knowledge Base can be defined *for purposes of Identifier selection*. Table G.2.1 provides a scope and an indication of the current status of the minimum specifications. The ‘Property’ refers typically to any characteristic, feature, attribute, or metric associated with a specific Identifier or its stack. Full definitions of these properties are provided in the Knowledge Base.

Table G.2.1 Summary of Important Knowledge Base Properties for Identifiers

Group	Property	Type	Values	Release
Definition	Count	Value	Value from Property table	1.1
Definition	Identifier Pattern	Value	Value from Resolver table	1.3
Definition	Namespace Unique	Value	Value from Resolver table	1.3
Definition	Scheme Type	Vocabulary	Value from Scheme table	1.3
Definition	Standard Type	Vocabulary	Value from Standard table	1.3
Definition	URL Pattern	Value	Value from Resolver table	1.3
Definition	URL_API	Value	Value from Resolver table	1.3
Definition	URL_Resolver	Value	Value from Resolver table	1.3

⁶⁹ Hugo, W., O Neill, E., Heinmann, N., & Priddy, M. (2025). DataSet - PID Knowledge Base [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14794355>

Functionality	Compact Identifier	Binary	Yes/ No	1.4
Functionality	Content Negotiation	Vocabulary	List of C.N. Options	1.3
Functionality	Disciplinary	Vocabulary	List of research domains	1.3
Functionality	Globally Unique	Binary	Yes/ No	1.1
Functionality	GUPRI	Value	Computed from Namespace, Resolvable, and Persistent properties	1.3
Functionality	Identifier Type	Vocabulary	Identifier Type	1.2
Functionality	Namespace	Vocabulary	Namespace Type	1.3
Functionality	Persistent	Binary	Yes/ No	1.1
Functionality	Resolvable	Binary	Yes/ No (Computed from resolver data)	1.1
Functionality	Sandbox	Binary	Yes/ No	1.4
Functionality	Scalability	Value	Computed from Number of Identifiers Issued	1.3
Functionality	Status	Vocabulary	Status Types	1.1
Governance	Coverage	Vocabulary	Extended Country List	1.2
Governance	Governance	Vocabulary	Governance Types	1.4
Governance	Membership Type	Vocabulary	Membership Type	1.4
Performance	Median Life (yrs)	Assessment	Computed from assessment data	1.4
Performance	Unresolved (%)	Assessment	Computed from assessment data	1.4
Service Topology	Resolution Topology	Vocabulary	Resolution Topology	1.3
Stack	Manager Count	Value	Number of Managers	1.3
Stack	Provider Count	Value	Number of Providers	1.3
Stack	Scheme Type	Vocabulary	Scheme Type Vocabulary	1.3
Stack	Standard Type	Vocabulary	Standard Type Vocabulary	1.3
Sustainability	Adopters	Vocabulary	Extended Country List	1.3
Sustainability	Adoption Status	Vocabulary	Adoption Typology	1.3
Sustainability	Business Model	Vocabulary	Business Model Type	1.4
Sustainability	Contingency	Binary	Yes/ No	1.4
Sustainability	Cost Recovery	Vocabulary	List of cost recovery types	1.4
Sustainability	Cost Recovery	Vocabulary	Cost Recovery Mechanisms	1.4
Sustainability	Focus	Binary	Yes/ No	1.4
Sustainability	National Adoption	Vocabulary	Country List	1.3
Sustainability	Start Date	Value	Establishment Year	1.3
Sustainability	Surplus	Binary	Yes/ No	1.4
Value Addition	API Services	Value	Computed from API URL	1.4
Value Addition	Metrics	Binary	Yes/ No	1.4
Value Addition	Multiple Resolution	Binary	Yes/ No	1.4